

standICT.eu 2026

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

FOLLOWING THE FELLOWS

**IMPACT REPORT FROM
FUNDED APPLICANTS TO
THE STANDICT.EU 2026
FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME**

EIGHT OPEN CALL

Editors:

Mona Marill, Maria Giuffrida, Gabriele
Quattrocchi, Teresa Ridolfi

NOVEMBER 2025

Disclaimer

This Impact report was produced by StandICT.eu 2026, a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project funded by the European Commission within the Research and Innovation Framework Programme Horizon Europe (HE), under grant agreement no.101091933. The information and views set out in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Commission and may not be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein. Reproduction is authorised, provided the source is acknowledged.

About StandICT.eu

The project is coordinated by [Trust-IT Srl](#) (IT) acting as a technical coordinator, and [Dublin City University](#) (IE) acting as financial coordinator, supported by its partners [AUSTRALO](#) (ES), [European Digital SME Alliance](#) (BE), [Fraunhofer](#) (DE) and [Open Forum Europe](#) (BE).

Acknowledgements

Our consortium is grateful to all our StandICT.eu 2026 community of experts for their competent work. This booklet is a tangible reflection of your continuous dedication to ICT Standardisation. Thank you!

StandICT.eu 2026 would also like to thank EC representatives **Carlos Lopez Rodrigues**, StandICT.eu 2026 Project Officer, **Paul Killeen**, **Emilio Davila-Gonzalez**, and **Thomas Reibe** for their leadership and guidance. The External Advisory Group (EAG) provided invaluable support throughout the course of the project. Our appreciation for their effort and commitment goes to **Silvana MacMahon** (EAG Chair), **Ana Garcia Robles**, **Betty XU**, **Diana Dus**, **Joel Myers**, **Karl Gruen**, **Lindsay Frost**, **Martin Chapman**, **Sandra Drechsler**, **Sebastian Hallensbelen**, **Silona Bonewald**, **Stephan Weisgerber**.

Finally, we would like to thank all our **EUOS Technical Working Groups** (European Observatory for ICT Standardisation) **chairs** and **members** for their investment in gathering expertise and producing outstanding landscape reports of the standardisation status across different ICT sectors.

■ Foreword

The European Green Deal & the New Industrial Strategy for Europe call for a strong EU presence in international Standardisation development. The recent significant shifts in the geopolitical environment call for increasing the intensity of the EU presence in international standardisation committees. Building up a strong and sustainable pool of European Standardisation competent professionals who are ready to engage in European and International Standardisation is crucial. With this we are pleased to contribute to this already engaged community through the “Following the Fellows” series Impact Reports, now in its 8th edition under the new StandICT.eu 2026 project, continuing the work of the precursor edition, proving a tangible testimony of the impact generated by European ICT experts working in collaboration with international Standardisation Developing Organisations (SDOs), thanks to the financial support provided through the StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme, as a paramount part of the broader mission of the StandICT.eu 2026 Coordination and Support Action.

The main purpose of these regular publications is to display the work carried out by our fellows and illustrate the demonstrable outcomes that excellent research can bring to both society and the economy (SMEs or industry at large). Therefore, we substantiate how each effort in which the fellows are engaged provides a potential benefit to society and contributes to achieving specific, desired societal outcomes because of the ICT Standardisation efforts.

As we move forward, our commitment to bolstering the EU’s role in international standardisation remains strong. The “Following the Fellows” series is not only a testament to the achievements of our fellows but also serves as an inspiration and a call to action for future standardisation professionals. By highlighting the critical work of these individuals, we aim to underscore the importance of ICT standardisation in driving innovation, ensuring competitive advantages, and contributing to the sustainability and resilience of society and the economy at large.

We invite the standardisation community, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and all interested parties to engage with the insights and findings presented in these reports.

Maria Giuffrida

StandICT.eu 2026 Project Coordinator,
Trust-IT Services Srl

■ Table of Contents

Foreword	2
Introduction	5
Overview of the Open Call #8.....	6
1. Foundational Drivers.....	8
Support for IETF transport protocol standardisation at the July 2025 Plenary Meeting.....	9
Contribution to e-identification and e-authentication at CEN/CLC/JTC 13 & ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG5's	11
Third edition of Rec. ITU-T X.510 ISO/IEC 9594-11, Protocol specifications for secure operations.....	13
Privacy preserving age assurance systems for online or in-person access to services or goods	15
Harmonisation of ISO TS 24946 and CEN/CLC/JTC19 WG3	17
2. Key Enablers.....	19
First Steps in Measurable Sustainability Modelling Standardization for AI-Enriched 6G.....	20
3GPP RAN ITU-R Ad-Hoc convenor.....	23
Chair of ETSI OpenCAPIF SDG	25
Towards EU AI Act Compliance: Data Quality and Bias in AI systems ..	27
IEEE P7018 - Requirements for trustworthiness and security of pretrained AI generative models (LLM).....	29
AI standardization roadmapping in support of the AI Act standardization request.....	31
AI-CoE Phase-III: Proof of Concept of the CoE Reference Model on Artificial Intelligence Adoption	33
Quantum Network Switching.....	35
Cybersecurity standards for AI systems in response to the EC standardisation request (AI Act)	37
AI, Quantum: Common Eu Standards For Ict Professional Skilling Across Technologies & Sub-Domains	39
Support for activities as the Convenor of the ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6 "Terminology Management and AI"	41
Enhancing AI Risk Management and QMS Standards for EU AI Act regulatory purposes in CEN/CENELEC	43
Taking the Micro-SME Voice into Securing Artificial Intelligence (SAI) Standardization Activities	45
Support for activities as the Project Leader of the TR "AI for Terminology Management".....	47
ISO 23042 - Decentralised identity management.....	49

EUDIW components requirements and guidelines, according to the risk assessment	51
Advancing Thing Description 2.0: Enhancing Affordances and more for Complex IoT Interactions	53
Request for funding for IETF IoT work	55
Completing the next steps in CBOR and CDDL	58
Quality of Service in IoT Architecture using the oneM2M Standard ..	60
Future of UHF RFID radio regulations - meeting new requirements from the European Commission	62
Actively contribute to ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC38 and IEEE S2ESC to harmonize standards across observability	64
3. Innovation for the Digital Single Market	66
New Sustainability standards within DLT & Blockchain Use - development of DLT Sustainability standards	67
The challenge of rewarding human creativity in the AI era	70
Mapping and Structuring the Standardisation Landscape of Virtual Worlds	72
IEEE SA HyperSpatial Transaction Protocol Spec Editor and Leadership (co-chair) of IEEE P2874 WG	74
4. Sustainable Growth	76
Harmonizing Digital Product Passports and Circular Business Models	77
Semiconductor and trusted chips landscape and gap analysis	79
Guidance on digitalisation and management of data in the maintenance of assets	81
Named address spaces for C	83
Virtual Worlds, 6G, Ethics and AI for Robotics and Autonomous Systems Standards	85
Robotics — Electrical interfaces — Connectivity interoperability for End-effectors	87
Standardization in Robotics and AI for Healthcare	89
5. Societal challenges	91
Towards standardization of air quality sensor systems	92
Participation in IEC TC 62/SC 62D/JWG 35/36 and TC 62/SC 62A/JWG 9 (Medical Robots and Medical AI)	94
Simulation in Additive Manufacturing- Guidance on computational methods for manufacturing industry	97
Global Health and Wellbeing Standard for Sustainable Cities: Integrating Digital Health	99

■ Introduction

This report details the outcomes of the eighth cohort of fellows supported by the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme. It shares perspectives and the first results of the fellowships that were financed by the 8th open call¹.

Our team is delighted to showcase this series of StandICT.eu 2026 fellowship stories, which feature the funded experts detailing the addressed standards and ICT landscapes, and how these will fill the identified gaps and impact the related stakeholders and society. The results obtained by our fellows fully respond to many of the objectives set out in the EU Strategy on Standardisation. They mainly prioritise and address standardisation needs in strategic ICT areas, enhance European leadership in global standards, support innovation and improve the overall integrity of the European standardisation system.

Standards are at the core of the EU Single Market and global competitiveness, and play a fundamental (if sometimes invisible) role in our daily lives. They can ensure the interoperability of products and services, reduce costs, improve safety, and foster innovation.

At the same time, standards act as powerful drivers for innovation and growth by helping researchers bring their innovations to market and disseminate technological advances, as standards make their results transparent and ensure high quality. One of the critical purposes of StandICT.eu 2026 is to support the activity of European ICT experts to contribute to the modernisation and consolidation of the European standardisation system as well as to the valorisation of their research outputs, to efficiently respond to the EU's ambitions towards different thematic ICT areas, such as Metaverse and Digital Product Passport, which were the focus of the announcement of the 8th Open Call.

The primary purpose of this document is to share the results attained through the work carried out by the 40 funded experts and to showcase the most relevant outcomes, creating awareness of the potential impact and repercussions of such effects on commerce, industry, governmental policies and strategies and society. This open call is the eighth out of nine StandICT.eu 2026 Open Calls. Each open call will have a dedicated impact report, demonstrating the key findings, contributions, and observations made with the StandICT.eu community, the European Commission, the Multi-Stakeholder Platform for ICT Standardisation, the SDOs, and other interested parties, including all actors within our ever-growing StandICT.eu community.

In this funding batch, **in total, 40 fellowships** were granted, tackling the five policy areas as defined in the ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan 2025²:

- ▷ **Foundational drivers:** 6 fellowships focusing on Cybersecurity (4 fellowships), and E-Privacy (2).
- ▷ **Key enablers and security:** 20 fellowships focusing on Artificial Intelligence (9 fellowships), 5G/6G (3), Data interoperability (1), Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature) (2), and Internet of Things (5).
- ▷ **Innovation for the Digital Single Market:** 4 fellowships focusing on Blockchain and DLT (2 fellowships), Web 4.0 and virtual worlds (2).
- ▷ **Sustainable growth:** 5 fellowships focusing on Robotics and autonomous systems (3), Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport (1), and ICT Environmental impact (1).

1 <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/standicteu-2026-8th-open-call>

2 <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2025>

Overview of the Open Call #8

This open call was running from February 10th, until April 11th, 2025. It received a record number of 105 applications, of which 40 were selected for funding, with an overall 319 390€ granted.

The StandICT.eu Open Calls target European ICT standardisation experts who contribute to international SDOs, work groups, and/or technical committees on any of the priority topics outlined in the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. Due to their current strategic importance at the EU level, applications focusing on the issues of Virtual Worlds and Digital Product Passport are highly encouraged. However, this open call was open for applications tackling a broad range of ICT domains (as encompassed in the ICT Rolling Plan for Standardisation) and treated equally.

Fellowship Profiles

The funded applications encompass a broad geographic spectrum, spanning 13 different EU or associated countries, with the majority of experts hailing from Spain, Germany and the United Kingdom. 16% of the funded experts are female, reflecting the broader context of ICT and standardisation professionals, where the majority of workers are male. Moreover, 28% of the financed fellows are new to the StandICT.eu programme, and the remainder are returning fellows who have already benefited from a funded StandICT.eu fellowship.

The retained fellowships are represented by a balance across key technologies and a broad spectrum of SDOs that will benefit from the applicants' competence and expertise. As outlined in the figure below, a large portion of the granted fellows have chosen their focus across various horizontal and vertical ICT areas; the most popular places in this batch include artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and internet of things. Moreover, this funding batch is marked by various vertical ICT areas the fellowships cover, namely circular economy (including digital product passport) and eHealth.

Figure 1 - Overview of the #8 Open Call key results and insights

Engaged SDOs, Organisations and European Projects

53% of the fellows' activity contributes to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs including ITU, IEEE, IETF, ISO and ISO/IEC while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC, with the German national standards body, DIN, and with international standardisation associations, including W3C ERCIM, 3GPP and oneM2M.

Finally, 11 European funded and innovation research projects are related to the engaged work in the OC#8 fellowships, focusing on different horizontal and vertical technologies.

Project name	ICT Area	Funding Programme	Related StandICT.eu Fellows
NOLEFA	Artificial intelligence	HorizonEurope	Rani Wazir
ARISA	Artificial intelligence	Erasmus+	Jutta Breyer
6G-SANDBOX	6G	the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) / HorizonEurope	David Artuñedo Guillén
IMAGINEB5G			
6GPATH			
SAFE6G			
EU4MEDTECH	eHealth	HorizonEurope	João Leitão Quintas
DTRIP4H	eHealth	HorizonEurope	
OPENVERSE	Virtual worlds	HorizonEurope	Christoph Runde
ViWISSO	Virtual worlds	EU	
TAILOR	eHealth	MSCA Doctoral Framework	Jan Veneman

Now, we are delighted to share with you the insights from our granted fellows' work – and we genuinely hope that these results encourage you to get involved in our StandICT.eu community and join our Fellowship Programme under our forthcoming Open Calls, the European Observatory for ICT Standards (EUOS) - via the Technical Working Groups (TWGs) delivering up-to-date landscape and gap analysis, and finally Standards Academy training future experts in ICT Standardisation.

Together, we shape and reinforce the European and international ICT standardisation arena!

1. Foundational Drivers

Support for IETF transport protocol standardisation at the July 2025 Plenary Meeting

Godred Fairhurst
Professor, University of Aberdeen
United Kingdom

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IETF Transport and Services Working Group

Role

Chair of the IETF Transport and Services Working Group

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This was a one-shot contribution to provide travel support for participation to the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), and specifically participation at the July 2025 plenary meeting in Madrid. I attended this meeting as an Internet Transport expert contributing work and progressing standards to support the evolution of the Internet and its support for enhanced resilience, authentication and privacy.

An in-person attendance at the technical sessions also allowed me to progress the work for which I am an editor: Qlog draft-ietf-tsvwg-careful-resume-qlog, a transport specification based on the “qlog” specification being developed by the IETF QUIC; and a recent work item in the IETF Congestion Control working group, “Increase of the Congestion Window when the Sender Is Rate-Limited” (draft-ietf-ccwg-ratelimited-increase).

In-person participation at this meeting is particularly important in my current role as an Area Director of the WIT Area, where I will help organise and oversee the meeting as a whole and specifically support the WIT area WG chairs in organising WG sessions and supporting cross-area review of emerging specifications.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Internet standards underpin a wide range of industries and services. These range from the massive transfers in Cloud and Edge Computing, CDN distribution, the transport of big/AI data, to the massive communication of tiny messages by the Internet of Things (IoT), navigation services, identification and trust services, etc. Each of these depends on the protocols and specification for the Internet transport service to ensure the protection of the performance and the reliability of the Internet applications operating over the Internet path. The IETF RFCs therefore frequently form normative specifications that are used across a range of industries.

RFCs are used to specify how 3GPP standards interact with the Internet protocol stack and are cited as normative references in 3GPP standards. 3GPP also recognises that additions or modifications are sometimes needed to ensure the IETF Internet specifications fulfil the needs of 3GPP, which results in development within an appropriate IETF working group.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

Development of new IETF secure and resilient standards are important for a digital society. Since the last IETF plenary meeting 74 documents had been approved for publication in the last quarter and 83 RFCs had been published. Two new IAB workshops were announced: Joint IAB/W3C Workshop on Age-Based Restrictions on Content Access and an IAB Workshop on IP Geolocation.

The importance of standards was evident in several meetings co-located with IETF-123. This including meetings with policy and regulators, a meeting on Multi-Stakeholder Forum on Internet Standards Deployment accompanied by an IEPG presentation by Rüdiger Martin of the Internet Governance Team from DG-CNECT, EU. This outlines plans around NIS2, and sought to develop understanding of challenges and barriers, provide timelines for deployments of protocols at scale and best current practice. The transport system is primarily concerned with robustness and resilience to disruption of the Internet service. IETF participants had various insights into the roll-out of new standards and the implications of the new regulatory landscape.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to a technical report entitled "Careful Resume (draft-ietf-tsvwg-careful-resume)" that specifies a cautious method for IETF transports that enables fast startup of congestion control for a wide range of connections, known as "Careful Resume".

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This fellowship supported my one-shot participation in IETF working meeting, and hence it can be considered successfully concluded.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/draft-ietf-tsvwg-careful-resume-qlog>

<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-tsvwg-careful-resume/>

<https://datatracker.ietf.org/person/gorry@erg.abdn.ac.uk>

Contribution to e-identification and e-authentication at CEN/CLC/JTC 13 & ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG5's

Christophe Stenuit

Expert in Cybersecurity, Viewconcept.be
Belgium

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC 27 WG 5 on Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection, Working Group 5 on Identity management and privacy technologies

CEN/CENELEC JTC 13 WG 5 on Cybersecurity and Data Protection, Working Group 5 on Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship aims of positively influence the European market and its infrastructures by benefiting from international contributions (e.g. ISO/IEC) in the controlling of civil security and the protecting of e-identity and e-privacy. I have contributed to enhancing existing references, and encouraged promoting the use of these references through adoption at the European market.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Through this fellowship, I have contributed to ease the implementation of e-identity and e-privacy developments. The scope of the proposed standardization activity includes proposing/revising/amending/reviewing standards. Progress was made on the following ICT standards:

- ▶ ISO/IEC 24760-1 about identity management terminology and concepts
- ▶ ISO/IEC 24760-2 about identity management architecture
- ▶ ISO/IEC 24760-3 about identity management practices
- ▶ ISO/IEC 29146 about A framework for access management
- ▶ ISO/IEC 29115 about Entity authentication assurance framework
- ▶ ISO/IEC SC27 WG 5 PWI 25860 studying on authentication and authenticators in the context of multi factors authentication and its positioning in the IAM context as a result of ISO/IEC 24760-4 project cancellation.
- ▶ Integration of the referred standards with their amendments
- ▶ Adoption of the referred standards as prEN when available

Other supporting activities were also carried out, e.g. contributions on supporting

standardisation activities in relation to, as part of the ISO JTC1 SC27 WG5: contributions to AG5 on strategy

And support to the analysis of ISO/IEC JTC 1 EDM process and submission of a proposal for a better efficiency in actions.

Finally, as part of the CEN/CLC/JTC 13/WG5, I have contributed to the establishment of a Liaison Statement of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG 5 to CEN-CENELEC JTC13 WG5.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

SME are better aware of risks and of controls required in IT and information protection. Recent EU GDPR, eIDAS2 regulation, DORA, and NIS-2 directives developments impose a different view on IT risks, information security, data privacy protection and identity management controls, and by this a different awareness of the consequences that may fall down improper compliance to good practices. Good standard references help confidence establishment and maturity improvement in matter yesterday far from SMEs' concerns.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. I supported systematic reviews, revisions, and amendments of existing work items, listed here above, as well as I contributed to the adoption and the dissemination of these work items at EU market, and by this guaranteeing the sustainability of existing references in a changing world.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Most developed texts are achieving maturity. Many editorial changes were introduced by the central ISO editorial management to adapt to the new ISO directives with little values and a lot of efforts. Another initiative was made to adopt projects as horizontal standards at ISO/IEC. The referred work items are being more and more used or referred in the industry and this will provide visibility to the projects. Some efforts are still required to achieve publications. This activity will continue over 2025, and achieve publications during 2025 and 2026. A later initiative is on its way for completing the series of standards. This initiative shall lead the activity until 2029.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2307986&cs=1BFE244DDA2A68D1B5C93795034A8DD05

Third edition of Rec. ITU-T X.510 | ISO/IEC 9594-11, Protocol specifications for secure operations

Erik Andersen

Consultant Andersen's L-Service
Denmark

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ITU-T Study Group 17 question 11, Security - Generic technologies to support secure applications
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6/WG 10, Telecommunications and information exchange between systems - Directory, ASN.1 and Registration

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Quantum-safe algorithms are being completed by ISI/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/WG 2, by NIST and by IETF. They need to be described formally in such a way that that can be referenced by protocols standards. Migration technique for cryptographic algorithm needs extended to cover more aspects. Migration techniques need urgently to be prepared so they are in place when quantum computers become a reality. The challenge is to provide implementable specifications that precisely describes the objective of the specification.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Rec. ITU-T X.510 | ISO/IEC 9594-11 is part of a horizontal cybersecurity trilogy also consisting of Rec. ITU-T X.509 | ISO/IEC 9594-8 (the framework for public-key infrastructure); and Rec. ITU-T X.508 | ISO/IEC 9594-13 (details on cryptographic algorithms, key management, and best practice for PKI establishment and maintenance). This trilogy needs to be constantly updated to keep pace with new challenges. They will later be supplemented by a new standard on decentralised public-key infrastructure (DPKI).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

The extended ITU-T X.510 | ISO/IEC 9594-11 is expected to be an important specification for cryptographic algorithm migration which is essential in the light of future developments of quantum computers. The cryptographic pluck-in capabilities are also important as they will ease migration, and they will allow different areas of the world to have their own choice of cryptographic algorithms. Moreover, this standard provides lean protocols with a minimum of overhead providing cybersecurity to other protocols (security by simplifications). This in particular important for constrained devices, like IoT devices.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

It is a proposal for updating an existing standard Rec. ITU-T X.510 | ISO/IEC 9594-11 to produce a new edition

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

ITU-T X.510 | ISO/IEC 9594-11 has three major objectives: Providing specifications for secure protocols for support of public-key infrastructure (PKI); formal specification of cryptographic algorithms to be included in protocols; and tools and principals for migration of cryptographic algorithms.

At a recent ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6 meeting it was decided to separate the migration part out to a new standard to improve visibility. This activity is under progress and the two part are now progressed together

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.itu.int/ITU-T/recommendations/rec.aspx?id=14320

Privacy preserving age assurance systems for online or in-person access to services or goods

Denis Pinkas

CEO, DP Security Consulting SAS
France

Sector

E-Privacy

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection WG5 Identity management and privacy technologies

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The addressed gap of this fellowship concern the need to check whether an individual meet an age-eligibility criteria, such as being over 18, happens in different contexts, e.g., while making an online access on the Internet, a local access to enter a space or a venue or to buy a product or a service from an unattended vending machine. For the moment, there exists no guidance on a global approach or solutions to deploy that address these needs while respecting the privacy of individuals.

Therefore, the priority is the support of age verification through the use of digital identity wallets at a worldwide level; i.e., not singly within and between the EU countries. We focus on defining a Framework by developing ISO 27566-1 in ISO SC 27 WG 5: Age assurance Systems: Framework (currently at FDIS stage).

In 2024, it has been proposed to launch ISO 27566-2: Technical approaches and guidance for implementation. Unfortunately, the vote for launching it failed, since one expert nominated by a NB was missing. This topic returned to the PWI stage. At the moment, I am preparing with the lead editor and the other co-editor a new draft and a FORM 4 to present it at the next meeting in Kunming (China) in September 2025.

Also, I contribute to ISO 27566 series is: ISO 27566-3. In March 2025, the title of this part was changed into "Approaches to comparison or analysis" (currently at WD stage).

Finally, I provide guidance to support age verification, age estimation and age inference. The focus will be on techniques supporting (1) age verification through the use of digital identity wallets and (2) age estimation performing a facial analysis while using AI (Artificial Intelligence).

The major faced challenge is that the digital credential related standards are developed in various of different committees, such as ISO TC 68, ISO SC 17, ISO SC27, IETF, W3C and OpenID Connect to name a few of them. Surprisingly, a worldwide Architecture Framework is missing. ISO SC 27 WG 5 is preparing a PWI for it.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I contribute to the ISO Standardization landscape, through the development of the ISO 27566 series: Age Assurance Systems, including the three parts:

- ▶ Part 1: Framework (at FDIS stage)
- ▶ Part 2: Technical approaches and guidance for implementation (at PWI Stage)
- ▶ Part 3: Approaches to comparison or analysis (at WD stage)

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

Access to pornographic content and age-restricted services or products available online, like alcohol, diets, self-harm or suicide information, needs to be better controlled. Legislation is necessary but will not be sufficient: efficient methods need to be put in place.

Two main categories of solutions are promising: age estimation using AI facial analysis and digital identity wallets.

The AI Act published in the Official Journal (OJ) of the European Union on 12 July 2024 considers applications using AI for age estimation as “high-risk applications”.

The EUDIW (EU Digital Identity Wallet) is expected to be usable for performing age verification in both online and proximity modes.

Besides these usages, age verification, estimation, or inference will be useful in other areas, such as controlling the age of teenagers or elderly people, so that they can obtain rebates. This will speed up controls and avoid the presentation of physical identity documents.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to further developing ISO 27566 series (Part 1, 2 and 3) as well as we presented a PWI 25863 “Exploration of digital wallets storing digital credentials”.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Some corrections will need to be made to the proposed draft for FDIS 27566-1. A NWIP for 27566-2 is being prepared among the three co-editors. A first WD and a FORM 4 are being prepared so that they can be presented and discussed in September 2025.

Moreover, the expert comments on 27566-3 are due in July 2025. Then, the three editors (including me) will need to prepare a DoC (Disposition of Comments) ahead of the meeting in Kunming.

A WD and a FORM 4 are being prepared for the PWI 25863 “Exploration of digital wallets storing digital credentials” so that they can be presented and discussed at the meeting in Kunming in September 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45306.html

Harmonisation of ISO TS 24946 and CEN/CLC/JTC19 WG3

Robin Renwick
Analyst Trilateral Research
Ireland

Sector

E-Privacy

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 307/JWG 4 Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG: Security, privacy and identity for Blockchain and DLT
CEN/CENELEC JTC19 Blockchain and DLT WG3 Personal identifiable information (PII) in Blockchain and DLT

Role

Other

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The fellowship tackles the lack of international, or European, standard or technical specification that focuses explicitly on privacy and data protection capabilities of DLT systems. With this regards, ISO TS 24946 “*Requirements and guidance for improving, preserving, and assessing the privacy capability of DLT systems*” has now reached CD stage (July 2025) and will endeavour to move through this process and be completed in 2026. This process requires continued support from experts to ensure delivery, as scheduled.

In this sense, the priority of this activity focuses at the European level, CEN/CENELEC JTC 19/WG3 to produce a European standard on PII protection within DLT which is strongly influenced by ‘DIN Spec 4997 - Privacy by Blockchain Design’ and the aforementioned ISO TS 24946. This European specification will seek to harmonise the GDPR and recent EDPB guidance to produce a technical specification intended for the European DLT ecosystem. This European specification will provide much needed clarity for the DLT ecosystem as regards data protection and privacy capabilities, affordances, and assessment. Further harmonisation between the international specification at ISO and the European standard will support interoperability, and ensure that privacy and data protection capabilities are harmonised globally.

The main challenges concerns exacting requirements from regulations such as Article 76(3) of MiCAR, as well as Article 79(1) of the European AMLR will require navigation. Standards require alignment and compatibility with those legal texts, as well as corresponding regulations regarding personal data, data markets, and trust services (e.g., GDPR, Data Act, eIDAS2). Ensuring there are no gaps between regulatory texts and the proposed European standards will be a primary focus.

Also, it must be ensured that there are no substantial gaps between international specifications and European standards will be the second focus. Standards alignment between ISO and CEN/CENELEC is viewed as a key outcome to benefit the global DLT ecosystem, and one that requires strong consensus building, given slightly different international privacy perspectives and preferences.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship enables me to contribute to the following activities:

- ▷ Development of “ISO/TC307/JWG 4/TS 24946 - Requirements and guidance for improving, preserving, and assessing the privacy capability of DLT systems”.
- ▷ Work at CEN/CLC JTC 19/WG 3 - Personal identifiable information (PII) in Blockchain and DLT”.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This fellowship supports wider European Digital strategy, as well as the European Annual Union Work Programme for standardisation. Personal data and privacy protection are fundamental cornerstones of European society, supported by strong public policy and legislative frameworks. Establishing the minimum requirements for privacy and data protection within DLT systems will provide the ecosystem with a baselines from which to ensure privacy and data protection rights are respected across Europe. This will influence financial services, digital identity, and data sovereignty across the whole European jurisdiction.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to new standards, as both “ISO/TC307/JWG 4/TS 24946 - Requirements and guidance for improving, preserving, and assessing the privacy capability of DLT systems” and “CEN/CLC JTC 19/WG 3 - Guidelines on processing PII using blockchain and distributed ledger technology” will be completely new standards/specifications.

They have never been produced before, and will be the first multi-national standards of their kind on the topic of privacy, data protection, and DLT systems.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The contributions to CD1 for “ISO/TC307/JWG 4/TS 24946 - Requirements and guidance for improving, preserving, and assessing the privacy capability of DLT systems” are stil ongoing. As well as my engagement to the development and content creation for first draft of “CEN/CLC JTC 19/WG 3 - Guidelines on processing PII using blockchain and distributed ledger technology”

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.iso.org/standard/88614.html

2. Key Enablers

The background is a complex digital landscape. It features glowing blue and green circuit traces on a dark blue base. Several concentric, glowing blue rings are scattered across the scene. A prominent feature is a glowing fingerprint scan, where the ridges of a finger are represented by a grid of white dots. To the right of the fingerprint, there are streams of binary code (0s and 1s) in white and blue, some appearing to flow or pulse. The overall aesthetic is high-tech and futuristic.

First Steps in Measurable Sustainability Modelling Standardization for AI-Enriched 6G

Muslim Elkotob

*Principal Solutions Architect and Standardization Expert,
Vodafone
Germany*

Sector

5G and Beyond (6G)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI TC INT Technical Committee (TC) Core Network and Interoperability Testing (INT)
ETSI AFI Autonomic Management and Control Intelligence for Self-Managed Fixed & Mobile Integrated Networks)

Role

Chair of ETSI TC INT

Vice-chair of ETSI AFI

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship targets to key gaps that are firstly, the lack of comprehensive KPIs that really assess the synergy impact from a holistic perspective when doing sustainability-by-design in 6G and AI-based applications and environments. Secondly, the lack of specific KVI (Key Value Indicators) that are able to capture societal and environmental value of complex systems and ecosystems, in order to prioritize and allocate resources properly.

Related to these, the challenge is to bring the requirements and inputs related to 6G, AI, and Sustainability from different SDOs and consolidating them properly into comprehensive KPIs and KVIs.

There, this activity focuses on the key priorities that include exploring the potential and streamlining for standardization the following discourses.

6G and AI Integration: The integration of 6G and AI focuses on enhancing and automating infrastructure, making it more intelligent and efficient. While this combination can significantly improve the operational aspects of communication networks, it lacks a crucial component—sustainability. Without a focus on sustainable practices, advancements in infrastructure remain incomplete and potentially harmful to environmental goals.

AI and Sustainability: These trends are inherently complementary, as AI can drive efficiency and innovation in sustainable practices. However, they can also be paradoxical. AI technologies often require significant computational power, which can lead to increased energy consumption and carbon emissions. Thus, this pairing, while promising, has limited potential unless carefully managed.

6G and Sustainability: The combination of 6G and sustainability addresses the need for eco-friendly communication networks. However, without the analytical and predictive power of AI, this integration lacks the sophistication needed to optimize resources and minimize environmental impact effectively.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The envisioned areas that comprise 6G, AI, and Sustainability are supported by a multitude of research streams and WGs across numerous SDOs. I conducted intensive research about the SDO landscape and summarized here the main findings:

6G and 6G-related:

- ▶ 3GPP SA2: network architecture and services, focusing on the system architecture & evolution, incl. slicing, SBA, integration of non-terrestrial networks.
- ▶ 3GPP RAN2 & RAN3: RAN arch.; support evolving needs 5G & 6G; integrated Edge
- ▶ ETSI ISG MEC: stand. open env.; multivendor service integration on Edge
- ▶ ETSI ISG F5G (5th Gen Fixed Networks): evolution arch., complement mobile 5G Artificial Intelligence

3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project)

- ▶ SA6: applications of AI in mobile networks, standardization of services & applications, that utilize AI & ML
- ▶ RAN WG3: AI for RAN optimization; interfaces for AI-based RAN improvements.

ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute)

- ▶ ISG ENI (Experiential Networked Intelligence): operator experience using AI; creating a standard reference model; defining critical datasets for AI-based systems.
- ▶ ISG ZSM (Zero-touch network & service management): automation; AI for network automation

ITU (International Telecommunication Union)

- ▶ ITU-T SG13 (Future Networks): frameworks and protocols for AI & ML

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

By interweaving 6G, AI, and sustainability, this project seeks to realize their full potential, driving innovation and progress in a way that isolated efforts cannot achieve. The creation of a collaborative platform and the focus on comprehensive performance metrics will facilitate the effective integration of these megatrends, fostering advancements that are both technologically superior and aligned with global sustainability goals.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not directly. My fellowship and its results are being documented into an ETSI TR document that captures the essence of my work. The main goals being exploring the dynamic interplay among three pivotal megatrends: 6G, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and sustainability. Each trend, when integrated with the others, transcends its individual capabilities, promising substantial progress beyond what pairwise combinations can achieve. The TR document streamlines the interactions between those trends and how they can enable blueprint use cases for leveraging the combined benefits and synergies of those trends.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

As a convenor and chair within ETSI AFI, I continue my engaged in:

- ▶ Driving Standardization Initiatives: Leading the development of standards, such as the ETSI Technical Report on Data Sharing Ecosystems, ensures alignment with industry needs and promotes interoperability.

- ▶ Facilitating Multi-SDO Collaboration: By leading the Multi-SDO stream on Autonomous Networks, I promote synergy among various standards development organizations, fostering cohesive advancements in autonomous network technologies.
- ▶ Championing Innovative Projects: Leading TM Forum Catalyst projects, including those focused on Generative AI and Green-AI, accelerates the practical application of AI in network management, contributing to sustainability and operational efficiency.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.etsi.org/committee/int>

 <https://portal.etsi.org/TB-SiteMap/INT/INT-WG-AFI-ToR>

■ 3GPP RAN ITU-R Ad-Hoc convenor

Giovanni Romano

*3GPP Expert, Novamint Ltd
United Kingdom*

Sector

5G and Beyond (6G)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

3GPP RAN ITU-R Ad-Hoc (3rd Generation Partnership Project, Radio Access Network, International Telecommunication Union – Radiocommunication Ad-Hoc group)
3GPP TSG RAN (3rd Generation Partnership Project Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network), chairing the sessions dedicated to ITU matters
3GPP TSG SA (3rd Generation Partnership Project Technical Specification Group System Aspects)
3GPP PCG (3rd Generation Partnership Project Project Coordination Group)

Role

Convenor of 3GPP RAN ITU Ad-Hoc

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship focuses on several key axes; including:

Firstly, the update of IMT-Advanced (aka 4G) and IMT-2020 (aka 5G) Recommendations; new Recommendation on IMT-2020 Satellite - Support the 3GPP Organization Partners activity for the documentation outside of 3GPP scope (e.g., IPR declarations, hyperlink to OPs' standards)

Secondly, the coordination of the follow-up activities to support the updates of the above Recommendations after 2025, and in particular aim to align the time-plan of WP5D and WP4B for the terrestrial and satellite components of IMT-2020

And finally to allow my SME company, Novamint, to participate to the 3GPP work on radio requirements and solutions for 6G

In particular, the activity on IMT-2020 Satellite will provide the regulatory documentation to allow the use of satellite 5G and satellite 5G-IoT solutions in countries that base their Regulations on ITU documents. As such this is a big opportunity for the European industry to influence the satellite technologies, by pushing standard 3GPP technologies against proprietary solutions developed outside Europe

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship is focusing on Key Enabler 5G and Beyond (6G) with several areas of relevance:

- ▶ 6G: Coordinate the ITU Ad-Hoc group where 3GPP will discuss the definition of the 3GPP radio Technical Performance Requirements. Attend as Novamint delegate to the definition of the activity (radio requirements and definition of the study phase on technical solutions) in 3GPP
- ▶ 5G and 5G satellite: co-ordinate the exchange of information between 3GPP and ITU-R

mainly on M.2150 (and M.2012 on 4G) and IMT-2020 satellite

- ▷ IoT, V2X (and others) in case ITU requests 3GPP inputs: Coordinate the correspondence between 3GPP and ITU
- ▷ New spectrum in case ITU requests 3GPP inputs: Support the discussion on technical parameters required to identify new bands for IMT and IMT satellite

ITU published in 2023 the Recommendation ITU-R M.[IMT.FRAMEWORK FOR 2030 AND BEYOND]. This document is the baseline for the definition of the requirements of IMT-2030, aka 6G. ITU-R published also the timeplan to arrive at the approval in 2030 of a new Recommendation containing the radio interface technologies for IMT-2030. 3GPP endorsed the document RP-232746 “High-level Considerations for 6G Timeline” stating that Studies for 6G in 3GPP are expected to start from Release 20. In March 2024 TSG RAN decided to aim to the definition of the radio Technical Performance Requirements (TPRs) in June. TSG RAN also decided that 3GPP will discuss the definition of the 3GPP TPRs in the ITU Ad-Hoc, a group that I coordinate. In June 2025, the 3GPP RAN plenary started the studies on technical solutions to fulfil the 6G requirements.

Satellite communications provide inclusion by reaching remote areas and ensure safety and communications during disasters and complement the terrestrial networks. It is important that standardised solutions are made available by 3GPP and then made into ITU Recommendations to provide a Regulatory framework for a large number of countries.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

European SMEs started to be quite active in 3GPP with the specification work of 5G, especially on aspects relevant to Verticals. In particular, SMEs are quite active in IMT-2020 satellite aspects and can benefit from the inclusion of 3GPP solutions in global standards defined by ITU

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. I am directly involved in coordinating and submitting the 3GPP contributions to ITU-R to update ITU-R Recommendation M.2012 (IMT-Advanced) and Recommendation M.2150 (IMT-2020). Moreover, I also work with the 3GPP exchange of information with ITU-R on the new ITU-R Recommendation on IMT-2020 satellite.

Finally, I also contribute to the definition of the IMT-2030 (aka 6G) radio requirements in 3GPP, by coordinating the group where they were discussed in preparation of RAN#108 (June 2025)

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The activity on the updates of M.2012, M.2150 and the new Recommendation on IMT-2020 satellite are progressing towards the finalization of the deliverables in ITU-R and new revisions in future. The activity on IMT-2030 Technical Performance Requirements moved after RAN#108 (June) from the ITU-R AD-Hoc to RAN plenary.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.3gpp.org/3gpp-groups/radio-access-networks-ran/ran-ah1>

Chair of ETSI OpenCAPIF SDG

David Artuñedo Guillén

*Head of Future Networks Lab at Telefónica I+D. S.A.u.
Spain*

Sector

5G and Beyond (6G)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

3GPP SA6 / S6-252502 Guidelines for 3GPP Application Enablement usage

ETSI Software Development Group (OpenCAPIF SDG)

ETSI Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC)

Role

Chair of ETSI OpenCAPIF SDG, member is other groups.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The evolution of 5G and beyond demands a cohesive and interoperable service enablement architecture that can address both network-driven and application-driven requirements across cloud and edge domains. In this context, the 3GPP SA6 working group has developed three key frameworks:

- ▶ CAPIF (Common API Framework) – a unified platform for exposing and managing APIs with standardized discovery, onboarding, and access control.
- ▶ EDGEAPP (Edge Application Enablement) – enablers that allow dynamic deployment, lifecycle management, and orchestration of applications at the network edge.
- ▶ SEAL (Service Enabler Architecture Layer) – a suite of enablers providing common services such as group communication, location, messaging, and configuration to applications across verticals.

While these frameworks have matured independently, industry stakeholders increasingly require guidance on how to deploy them in combination, to avoid functional duplication, enable coherent service orchestration, and ensure compatibility across operators and infrastructure providers.

For the developer community, the lack of consistent cross-framework guidelines hinders adoption and slows down the ecosystem's evolution. By providing explicit guidelines, this Technical Report will lower barriers to entry, streamline service design, and accelerate application innovation across verticals.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I support the creation of a new external TR (TR 23.947) that describes the integration between the 3GPP frameworks and services at the application enablement layer for key vertical specific use cases (including V2X, UAV and smart factory) that can leverage such integration.

The TR creation has been approved during SA6 meeting #67 at Fukuoka (Japan).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The new TR will provide Guidelines for SMEs in Europe to develop Applications and Services based in 3GPP SA6 API frameworks. This alignment of OpenCAPIF to the standard is critical to provide European Developers a consistent framework where the 3GPP CAPIF Guidelines will instruct European Developers on how to use CAPIF, and OpenCAPIF as the practical and open source reference implementation for European Developers to use it for Development, Integration and Testing of European Applications for 5G Networks. European companies do have an Open Source implementation of CAPIF to develop Applications and Services compatible with 5G standard API Exposure making their products more competitive.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to a new standards, namely TR 23.947 Guidelines for 3GPP Application Enablement usage.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I have presented this initiative at ETSI MEC Plenary meetings and in Open CAPIF Plenary meeting in June. The TR has been approved at SA6 WG and it will be further developed in the coming months, beyond June 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.3gpp.org/3gpp-groups/service-system-aspects-sa/sa-wg6

 <https://ocf.etsi.org/>

 www.etsi.org/technologies/multi-access-edge-computing

Towards EU AI Act Compliance: Data Quality and Bias in AI systems

Rania Wazir

*Co-Founder and CTO, leiwand AI gmbh
Austria*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG3 “Engineering Aspects”

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship contributes to two CEN/CENELEC projects, in response to the European Commission’s Standardisation Request, including “Quality and governance of datasets in AI” (datasets) and “Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems” (bias).

Given the hard deadlines presented by the upcoming EU AI Act, and the necessity of having appropriate standards in place, the timely completion of the projects is a top priority. The tight deadline, however, is a significant challenge; speed is antithetical to consensus-based work. Furthermore, both of these standards build on other standards-in-progress, such as the Risk Management standard under development in Working Group 2.

The gaps identified in existing standards, which need to be addressed within the framework of the CEN/CENELEC projects, include metrics, relevance, completeness, and correctness (as outlined in the NWIP Form 4). For the bias standard, since TS 12791 addresses only classification and regression systems, the CEN/CENELEC work needs to cover a broader range of AI systems, and define metrics and measures not available in the existing standards.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship contributes to two CEN/CENELEC projects, in response to the European Commission’s Standardisation Request (SR) in support of the EU AI Act:

- “Quality and governance of datasets in AI” (datasets),
- “Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems” (bias)

These standards support, in particular, SR 2 on data and data governance, which includes also a request for procedures and methods to detect biases in data.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

As co-founder of an AI start-up and a consortium partner in research projects involving other SMEs, I am very aware of the importance of clear and simple guidelines that can help smaller organisations comply with regulations. SMEs often lack the resources to identify appropriate methods for compliance through extensive research.

This project should therefore have a positive impact on SMEs ability to govern and use data correctly, and to produce and assess bias in AI systems, thus simplifying compliance with the AI Act requirements.

Impact on Society

The bias and datasets standards support the European Commission's standardisation request two on data and data governance. Such a standard is beneficial to consumers, who can rely on quality products and be protected from discrimination, as well as to regulators and auditors, who will benefit from the fact that AI system developers adopt more systematic approaches to data governance and bias risk management.

My work on other standards, such as 23282, supports the SR on accuracy, while 12792 supports the standardisation request 4 on transparency. Transparency helps downstream providers and system integrators build safe systems, helps deployers use systems properly, and assists auditors and regulators in carrying out their oversight duties.

Finally, just as I have benefited from the experience of other standards experts in learning about standardisation, I feel it is my turn to give back. Whether as project editor, as head of delegation attending plenaries, or as expert participating in working group discussions, I am happy to share knowledge and experiences with those who are new to standardisation.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I have contributed as project editor to two standardisation projects:

- ▷ ISO/IEC 12792 Transparency taxonomy of AI systems, in ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 WG3 (parallel development with CEN/CENELEC JTC21, ISO lead)
- ▷ ISO/IEC 23282 Evaluation methods for accurate natural language processing systems, in ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 JWG5 (parallel development with CEN/CENELEC JTC21, ISO lead)

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The bias and datasets projects are both expected to achieve a level of maturity sufficient for national body commenting by fall 2025. Final NB voting and publication are currently set for the first quarter of 2027.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://jtc21.eu/working-groups/>

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:110:0:::FSP_PROJECT,FSP_LANG_ID:80364,25&cs=1666F657E6EA4C65ACCF18A2D31F38C1A

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:110:0:::FSP_PROJECT,FSP_LANG_ID:80353,25&cs=18339D53B8C5ECC6D02462B4E4B20EDBB

<https://www.iso.org/standard/84111.html>

<https://www.iso.org/standard/87387.html>

IEEE P7018 - Requirements for trustworthiness and security of pretrained AI generative models (LLM)

Andrea Basso
CTO, Synesthesia s.r.l.
Italy

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE P7018 - Standard for Security and Trustworthiness Requirements in Generative Pretrained Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my contribution to the development of IEEE P7018 - Standard for Security and Trustworthiness Requirements in Generative Pretrained Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models. This new standard tackles several key gaps and challenges, including:

- ▶ **Unified Standards Framework:** The AI landscape currently suffers from fragmented security and trustworthiness practices for generative models. This lack of standardization hinders cohesive development. Our proposed framework addresses this gap by establishing comprehensive standards that cover the complete AI model lifecycle.
- ▶ **Privacy Protection and Regulatory Alignment:** In Europe's strict regulatory environment, particularly under GDPR, privacy protection is critical. These standards implement robust data handling protocols to prevent privacy breaches while ensuring full compliance with current and forthcoming data protection laws.
- ▶ **Building Public Confidence:** Clear standards are essential for fostering trust in AI technologies and achieving market adoption. Without them, users remain skeptical. By defining requirements for transparency, interpretability, and explainability, these standards make AI models more understandable and trustworthy to the public.
- ▶ **Harmonizing Cross-Sector Adoption:** Different European sectors have adopted AI at varying rates, resulting in inconsistent practices. This framework provides flexible yet consistent standards that can be applied across all industries, ensuring uniform security and trustworthiness benchmarks for generative AI models.
- ▶ **Strengthening Global Competitiveness:** Europe must maintain its position in the global AI race. Standardization not only creates internal alignment but also enhances international competitiveness by ensuring European AI innovations meet global benchmarks, thereby amplifying Europe's influence in shaping the worldwide AI ecosystem.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The foundation of this work is IEEE P7018, which establishes requirements for the trustworthiness and security of pretrained generative AI models, including LLMs. Our activities involve interactions with relevant ISO and CEN/CENELEC standards bodies.

This ICT standardization initiative seeks to establish robust frameworks that ensure the security and trustworthiness of generative AI models. The project carries special importance for Europe, driven by three key factors: the rapid integration of AI technologies across European sectors, Europe's commitment to ethical AI development and data protection, and its pioneering regulatory leadership through the EU AI Act.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

This standard has European Strategic Importance that includes notably sector-wide implementation and strengthening privacy infrastructure.

Firstly, regarding sector-wide implementation, AI technologies are becoming deeply embedded in Europe's core industries—including services, healthcare, finance, ICT, and transportation. With the growing dependence on generative models in these critical sectors, establishing trustworthiness standards is no longer optional but essential. A standardized approach ensures consistent, ethical, and responsible AI implementation across all application domains.

Secondly, related to strengthening privacy infrastructure, Europe has established itself as a global leader in privacy protection through GDPR and the EU AI Act. The proposed standards reinforce this regulatory ecosystem by specifically targeting vulnerabilities like data breaches and unauthorized access to sensitive information. This creates a harmonized framework that both facilitates regulatory compliance and strengthens public confidence in AI systems across EU member states.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. I work on IEEE P7018 - Requirements for trustworthiness and security of pretrained AI generative models (LLM) that is a new proposed standard part of the series 7000 of IEEE in the area of AI

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I am task leader for the compliance section of IEEE 7018. We are currently reviewing the gap analysis with respect to existing ISO and CEN/CENELEC standards. As a next step, we will continue with this work by sharing current drafts with external stakeholders for feedback resulting to enhanced technical sections of this standard.

Online references related to the fellowship work

[https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7018/11306/#:~:text=Standard%20for%20Security%20and%20Trustworthiness,Pretrained%20Artificial%20Intelligence%20\(AI\)%20Models&text=This%20standard%20establishes%20a%20comprehensive,of%20generative%20pretrained%20AI%20models.](https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7018/11306/#:~:text=Standard%20for%20Security%20and%20Trustworthiness,Pretrained%20Artificial%20Intelligence%20(AI)%20Models&text=This%20standard%20establishes%20a%20comprehensive,of%20generative%20pretrained%20AI%20models.)

AI standardization roadmapping in support of the AI Act standardization request

Patrick Bezombes
Independent Consultant
France

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence WG 1 Strategic Advisory Group (SAG)
CEN/CENELEC JTC 21/WG4 Foundational and societal aspects

Role

Convenor of CEN/CENELEC JTC 21/ WG4

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The main objective of my activity is to monitor, support and adapt, if necessary, the CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 Work Programme in response to the AI standardization request. Given the complexity of the AI standards relationship and the complexity of the AI trustworthiness concept, it is essential to monitor the standards development timelines, the coverage of the standardization request, the interplay and relationship between JTC 21 standards. The JTC 21 standards development timelines are closely reviewed by the European Commission.

Given the JTC 21 situation and the strategic impact of the AI standardization for the EU, the standardization activities are very closely monitored by EC representatives. JTC 21 leadership meets EC representatives on a very regular basis.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The standards that I am dealing with are:

- ▶ prEN XXX (WI=JT021039) Quality management system for EU AI Act regulatory purposes (SR 9)
- ▶ prEN 18228 (WI=JT021024) AI Risk Management (SR1)
- ▶ prEN 18229 (WI=JT021008) AI Trustworthiness Framework (SR 3 to 7)
- ▶ prEN XXX (WI=JT021029) Cybersecurity specifications of AI Systems (SR 8)
- ▶ prEN XXX (WI=JT021036) Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI Systems (SR 2)
- ▶ prEN XXX (WI=JT021037) Quality and governance of datasets in AI (SR 2)
- ▶ prEN XXX (WI=JT021038) AI Conformity Assessment (SR 10)
- ▶ prEN ISO/IEC 24970 (WI=JT021021) AI System Logging
- ▶ prEN (WI=JT021024) Evaluation methods for accurate computer vision systems
- ▶ ISO/IEC CD 4213 Performance measurement for AI classification, regression, clustering and recommendation tasks
- ▶ ISO/IEC CD 24029-3 Assessment of the robustness of neural networks — Part 3: Methodology for the use of statistical methods

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The future JTC21 harmonized standards will impact every organisations involved in high-risk AI systems and willing to put their product on the EU market. Those future harmonised standards aim also at protecting health, safety and fundamental rights and have therefore an impact on European societies.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute in anticipating new harmonised AI standards. Following exchanges with the European Commission, a new deliverable is being prepared by WG1 to cover the delays of the development of JTC 21 harmonised standards. This project aims at informing and preparing organisations to the arrival of harmonised standards in support of the AI Act. In light of recent developments, it appears that JTC 21 harmonised standards will not be delivered before the end of 2026.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Yes, I am developing the new work item proposal on “AI trustworthy: Overview and harmonised standards”, and I am also a contributor on the preliminary draft.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2916257&cs=11D701467243B7C63DEF4702C86E0138A

AI-CoE Phase-III: Proof of Concept of the CoE Reference Model on Artificial Intelligence Adoption

Javier Peris

ICT Senior Advisor, Consultant and Trainer; Business, Technology & Best Practices, S.L.

Spain

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

UNE ICT mirror subcommittees for: ISO/IEC JTC 1 (ICT), subcommittees SC40 (ICT Management), WG 7 Centres of Excellence.

Role

Chair of UNE CTN 71/SC 40 and Convenor of SC 40/WG 7 on AI Centers of Excellence.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my engagement in a standardisation projects that has the main priority focused on helping organisations to drive innovation and technological transformation using the Centre of Excellence (CoE) as the best management mechanism in a context of a shortage of professional profiles with expertise in Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive technologies.

Moreover, the AI expansion must overcome important gaps such as:

- ▶ The high failure rate in AI initiatives (80% according HBR 2021).
- ▶ The knowledge reside inside specialised vendors and not in the organisations.
- ▶ More importance is given to the technology than to the benefit it brings to the business.
- ▶ It is difficult to reuse experiences in an organisation.
- ▶ There is no standardised way on how to adopt and implement AI-based solutions.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This activity is continuation to a previous fellowship funded under open call 5. I am working on the validation via PoC (Proof of Concept) of a new standard that facilitates the AI adoption. These new standard on CoE in AI will enable companies to improve in two key areas: 1) to early expand AI utilisation and 2) to reduce the high risk of failure of AI initiatives.

Today, there are no international standards that address how to apply AI successfully across an organisation's multiple activities. These CoE on AI adoption standards serie will be useful specially for small organisations, but also for large corporations.

This new standard under evaluation via PoC will generates an updated version of the draft: UNE-71406 "Centres of Excellence to drive Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive change - Implementation Guidelines. Technical Specification".

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

European small organisations do not have the experts or economic resources to hire specialised AI consultants, so they must postpone the application of AI in their businesses. This generates a new delay in their innovation gap. The main opportunity for SMEs is their incorporation to a future sectorial cluster type, laboratory of a City Hall, and other potential movements of knowledge collectivisation.

Creating a standard on how to constitute and manage an AI Center of Excellence enables European small companies to have a higher success rate in AI innovation initiatives, making them easier to realise and reducing risk.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

This initiative is working on the validation of a new of standard that facilitates the AI adoption via the use of Centre of Excellence management model in order to centralise and share expertise.

The new standard validated via PoC will be: UNE-71406 “Centres of Excellence to drive Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive change - Implementation Guidelines. Technical Specification”.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

In order to solve the challenge of facilitating the success of AI solution implementation, this initiative proposes to use the Center of Excellence (CoE) best practices model. A CoE as the path to orchestrate the business portfolio of AI initiatives while facilitates expertise sharing . The objective is to offer public administrations, institutions, corporations, SMEs, universities, non-profit organisations, etc. a detailed vision of the different successful approaches for the incorporation of Artificial Intelligence for the transformation of organisations and for the development of new business models.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.une.org/encuentra-tu-norma/comites-tecnicos-de-normalizacion/comite?c=CTN+71/SC+40>

Quantum Network Switching

Jessica Illiano

*Assistant Professor, University of Naples Federico II
Italy*

Sector

Quantum technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IRTF Quantum Internet Research Group

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Within this fellowship, the activities have been focused on bridging the gap in a shared formulation of the switching functionality for quantum networks and its logical responsibilities. Quantum Internet represents one of the most significant emerging fields in ICT, promising transformative advances in communication, computation, and security. The inclusion of the Quantum Internet as a strategic priority within the European Quantum Flagship initiative underscores its relevance to long-term European objectives, such as leadership in quantum technologies and the establishment of a robust quantum communication infrastructure.

Despite this importance, critical challenges remain in aligning research contributions with the needs of standardisation. Current global activities on quantum networking focus heavily on establishing baseline architectural principles, as exemplified by QIRG discussions, but fall short in addressing granular but essential aspects, such as switching functionality. In particular, the terminology used to describe these functionalities often lacks specificity or consensus, as clearly identified within this fellowship investigation.

The lack of coherent terminology and standardized frameworks hinders collaboration and risks slowing down standardization progress. A common language and agreed-upon functionality are critical for fostering collaboration between European institutions and for ensuring compatibility between their contributions and global frameworks. The relevance of this activity lies in addressing these foundational gaps.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The efforts in providing commonly agreed upon definition and identifying boundaries and responsibilities of network devices and functionality can be recognized as activities closely related to ICT standardization processes. Accordingly, the activities of this project are well aligned with the ICT standard landscape, focusing on the formalization and harmonization of terminology, functional roles, and operational models for network devices.

This work is particularly relevant in the context of quantum technologies and quantum networking, a field still in its early stages of development-- with respect to classical network -- where shared reference models, clear definitions, and consistent terminology are essential to assist an efficient cooperation between different research areas and industry. Through the clarification of the scope and functionality of devices such as quantum switches, routers, and repeaters -- and by mapping their logical responsibilities to potential functional layers -- the

project supports the reduction of ambiguity and a cross-disciplinary understanding.

The approach taken directly supports ongoing activity within recognized bodies such as the IRTF Quantum Internet Research Group (qirg) and is coherent with approved documents such as RFC9340 “Architectural Principles for a Quantum Internet” and RFC 9583 “Application Scenarios for the Quantum Internet”.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

The advancement of quantum technologies and quantum networks is closely connected to human rights, particularly regarding cybersecurity concerns. However, the specific activities associated with this fellowship do not directly address societal impacts. This distinction arises from the maturity of the concepts involved—such as networking functionalities—as well as the timeline and objectives outlined in the proposal.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not directly. The activities are expected to result in two research papers, one survey paper concerning the collected literature review and glossary, another technical paper proposing a modeled solution to switching functionality.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This action should be continued, as can be noted by the challenges identified within the activity of this fellowship, the development of a standardized quantum network architecture requires further multidisciplinary heterogeneous efforts coming from both academic research and industry.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.irtf.org/qirg.html>

Cybersecurity standards for AI systems in response to the EC standardisation request (AI Act)

Francisco Medeiros-Filho

Independent expert, FM Tech Consult BV
Belgium

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Role

Head of the Belgian delegation at CEN/CENELEC JTC21
Co-convenor of JTC21 WG1 Strategic Advisory Group
Co-convenor of JTC21 WG5 Cybersecurity for AI Systems

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Recital 121 of the AI Act (EU Regulation 2024/1689 of 13 June 2024) states that “*standardisation should play a key role to provide technical solutions to providers to ensure compliance with this Regulation, in line with the state of the art, to promote innovation as well as competitiveness and growth in the single market. Compliance with harmonised standards, which are normally expected to reflect the state-of-the-art, should be a means for providers to demonstrate conformity with the requirements of this Regulation*”.

The AI Act shall apply from 2nd August 2026. Therefore, the standardization work carried out by CEN/CENELEC JTC21 will have a direct impact on the industry, especially in the field of cybersecurity for AI systems. The relevance of the proposed work is due to the pressing need to have cybersecurity standards for AI systems available as soon as possible so that stakeholders may demonstrate compliance with the legal obligations imposed by the AI Act, as described below:

Article 15.5 of the AI Act: *high-risk AI systems shall be resilient against attempts by unauthorised third parties to alter their use, outputs or performance by exploiting system vulnerabilities. The technical solutions aiming to ensure the cybersecurity of high-risk AI systems shall be appropriate to the relevant circumstances and the risks. The technical solutions to address AI specific vulnerabilities shall include, where appropriate, measures to prevent, detect, respond to, resolve and control for attacks trying to manipulate the training data set (data poisoning), or pre-trained components used in training (model poisoning), inputs designed to cause the AI model to make a mistake (adversarial examples or model evasion), confidentiality attacks or model flaws.*

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Standards and technical reports being drafted by ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 and CEN/CENELEC JTC13 have been used as input, whenever relevant. However, there is a lack of specific standards covering the field of cybersecurity for AI systems. Hence, the importance of the CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 (Cybersecurity for AI Systems) work to develop the necessary deliverables in the context of the EC Standardization Request on Cybersecurity for AI Systems (Commission Implementing Decision amended on 26 June 2025).

ISO/IEC JTC1/ SC27 is in the process of adopting a Technical Report ISO/IEC 27090. This deliverable is intended to provide guidance to organizations concerning AI-specific

vulnerabilities. However, TR 27090 only provides guidance to organizations; hence it does not respond to the EC Standardisation Request.

The most recent version of the cybersecurity standard for AI systems will be submitted for Public Enquiry (ENQ) by the end of September 2025. During the following 12 weeks, national standardisation bodies (CEN/CENELEC members) will have the opportunity to comment on the draft standard developed by CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The AI Act highlights the importance of EU harmonised standards and conformity assessment for the industrial stakeholders, for both providers and deployers, as well as users of AI systems. European harmonised cybersecurity standards for AI systems need to be developed and adopted, as a matter of urgency, for the benefit of the European industry, including SMEs and startups, as well as users of AI systems. It is important to demonstrate the trustworthiness of AI systems. Cybersecurity is just one of the aspects of trustworthiness.

Impact on Society

It is well known that the widespread use of AI systems is bound to have a significant impact on society. This subject has been debated at length by different academic, industrial, and governmental organizations. Cybersecurity for AI systems, although being just one of the aspects, is essential to demonstrate the trustworthiness of AI systems, hence providing assurance to users and consumers (societal impact).

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. The original standard on cybersecurity specifications for AI systems is about to be submitted early in October 2025 for public enquiry (ENQ phase over 12 weeks). This is indeed a global milestone.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

After the 12 weeks period under the ENQ stage, CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 will address the comments received from the public enquiry phase. Once this is done, the formal adoption of the standard will happen in good time for the 2nd August 2026 application date of the AI Act.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.cencenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/artificial-intelligence

AI, Quantum: Common Eu Standards For Ict Professional Skilling Across Technologies & Sub-Domains

Jutta Breyer

*Consultant and Director, Breyer Publico SL
Spain*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/TC428 Digital competences and ICT Professionalism WG2
Competences, knowledge, skills and roles
CEN/TC428 WG3 Certification
CEN/TC428 WG4 Business, Strategy and outreach

Role

Convenor of CEN/TC428 WG2 and expert member in other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Digital and ICT Professional skills and competence performance play a vital role for the European economy and society as a whole, and dedicated EU reference standards that can be used by all ecosystem key stakeholders and across technologies, sectors and sub-domains are essential. The EC's Digital Compass based upon the Digital Strategy estimates a need of 20 million digital specialists by 2030, requiring massive investment and coordinated action for digital professional workforce development at all levels. In this highly demand-driven environment, CEN/TC428 "ICT Professionalism and digital competences" hosts and maintains a fundamental set of European standards delivering to the ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan. The standards provide the needed common language and reference point for all parties to act upon, giving a common basis for ICT professional workforce development across Europe in the short, mid and long-term: EN16234 e-Competence Framework (e-CF), CWA16458 (ICT Profiles) and EN17748 (Foundational Body of Knowledge). From a European and Digital Single Market perspective, it is crucial to boost understanding across the entire eco-system that these three ICT full domain covering key standards are horizontal, technology-independent and product neutral, for easy application vertically into any specific technology and/ or business (sub-) domain. This fellowship focusses on increasing awareness and accelerating joint coordinated action across specific technology fields by making common usage of EN16234 e-CF standard series. Taking the AI field as current example, systematic collaboration with other organisations and committees is the way forward to leverage the full ICT domain covering TC 428 standards in specific digital technology fields (e.g. AI, cloud, quantum, security). This leads to collaborative solutions to common concerns and sectoral needs, as well illustrated by the successful e-CF uptake in ENISA European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The three main standards forming the horizontal background to this fellowship, hosted and maintained by CEN/TC428 "ICT Professionalism and digital competences" as a key contribution to the EC's Digital Strategy and to the ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan, are:

▶ EN16234 e-Competence Framework (e-CF) — A common Framework for ICT professionals

in all sectors (4 parts, latest version published in 2019);

- ▷ EN 17748 Foundational Body of Knowledge for the ICT Profession (2 parts, 2022)
- ▷ CWA 16458 ICT Professional Role Profiles (4 parts, latest CWA version published in 2018 with update by EN16234-1:2019 Annex, for transfer into EN)

The horizontal standard design makes them suitable for vertical contextualisation into different technologies (e.g., AI, Cloud, Quantum), sub-domains (e.g., Cybersecurity) and business fields (e.g. e-Health, Defence, Fintech). In practice, these standards are adopted by the user community across the full ICT and digital professional domains, from industry, qualification, research and policy viewpoints. In support of an efficient and sustainable European standardisation strategy, collaboration and inner-consistency of digital skills standardisation activities across related TCs is therefore key. Taking AI as a current, highly relevant example, inner-consistency in activities of CEN/TC428, CEN/CLC JTC21 AI and the new CEN WS "AI Role Profiles and Educational Profiles" are in the focus of this fellowship. The result will provide valuable practice and guidance for transfer to other committees and technology domains, taking quantum as a most recent example of new upcoming technology. There is a lot of standardisation work being done on topics like AI, Quantum and Security, and these need input and help in terms of defining the skills needs for those topics. Intensified collaboration between TC428 and JTC21 will accelerate the AI skills standardisation process on all levels and bring this mutual benefit to the entire European digital landscape.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Digital and ICT Professional skills performance play a vital role for the European economy and society, and dedicated EU reference standards are essential. SME's form the backbone of the economy in Europe, with almost two-thirds of employees in the EU working for an SME. SMEs often struggle with digital transformation and the optimal use of AI due to limited resources. Clear references and frameworks for skills and roles requirements for the digital and AI domain can be an essential aid for small and medium-sized enterprises when planning, recruiting and developing staff. The standards also provide the common language needed to interact with education providers and policy makers to understand and raise awareness on SME specific skills needs dealing with AI and digital more in general as well as with other specific technologies, and to find from there efficient and effective ways to get the right staff.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute actively to several ongoing standardisation projects, including essentially:

- ▷ EN16234 e-Competence Framework (e-CF) — A common Framework for ICT professionals in all sectors.
- ▷ EN 17748 Foundational Body of Knowledge for the ICT Profession.
- ▷ CWA 16458 ICT Professional Role Profiles.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Notably a systematic collaboration on TC428/JTC21 liaison and further interaction level has been started in order to ensure JTC21 AI skills related NWI/ standards developments and TC428 standards are provided in an inner-consistent way. Moreover, for TC428, considering AI relevant aspects in next EN16234 a.o. standard updates in line with JTC21 and AI WS evolutions will be an essential input to standards review.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:1218399&cs=16D21D7497970A5A38FB4CCE737358BFE

Support for activities as the Convenor of the ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6 “Terminology Management and AI”

Mohamed Khemakhem

CEO, MandaNetwork

France

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 37/SC 3 Management of terminology resources WG 6
Terminology Management and Artificial Intelligence

Role

Convenor of ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my role as convenor of ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6. And this activity tackles the following gaps:

- ▶ **Poor Integration of Terminology in AI Workflows:** There is limited guidance on how curated terminologies can or should be embedded into AI systems, impairing the accuracy and domain relevance of these technologies.
- ▶ **Lack of Interoperability:** Existing AI-driven terminology tools are often proprietary and do not align with established standards like TBX or TMF, leading to fragmentation and limited scalability.
- ▶ **Underexplored Ethical and Sociolinguistic Dimensions:** There is insufficient attention to bias, representation of minority languages, and the cultural sensitivity of AI-generated terminology.

The priorities for this engagement are:

- ▶ **Mapping and Evaluation of Current AI Methods:** Identifying which AI-enabled terminology management tasks (e.g., term extraction, concept definition, concept relation identification) are most valuable and mature for fast-track development.
- ▶ **Standards Development for Integration:** Developing best practices and potential standardization pathways to facilitate the integration of standardized terminology into AI systems.
- ▶ **Ethics and Inclusivity:** Promoting ethical practices in AI terminology management to reduce bias and enhance inclusivity across languages and cultures.

Finally, the key challenges are related to three aspects:

- ▶ **Technical Complexity and Rapid Technological Change:** Keeping pace with evolving AI capabilities, such as LLMs and semantic systems, while ensuring robust, maintainable standards.
- ▶ **Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration:** Bridging expertise from linguistics, AI, and domain-specific fields to ensure the standards are both technically sound and practically applicable.

- ▶ Stakeholder Engagement and Capacity Building: Attracting and involving the right mix of contributors—particularly from the AI community—and ensuring awareness and adoption of standards in real-world systems.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

As Convenor of ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6, my funded work contributes directly to the ICT standards landscape by leading the development of structured, standards-aligned guidance on how AI and terminology management can mutually enhance one another. The group explores how AI can support terminology processes—such as term extraction, concept definition, and term clustering—while also studying how structured terminological data can improve the accuracy, relevance, bias mitigation, and explainability of AI systems.

Our primary output, ISO/AWI TR 25896 “AI for Terminology Management,” is being developed in close collaboration with terminology and AI experts (and this activity is at the core of my second fellowship funded under this same batch).. By bridging established language practices with emerging technologies like machine learning and natural language processing, the project promotes interoperability, scalability, and ethical AI adoption across multilingual digital environments.

As Convenor, I coordinate the integration of these standards into our deliverables and guide cross-disciplinary contributions. This work not only strengthens current ICT standardization efforts but also lays the foundation for future developments at the intersection of AI, linguistics, and data-driven communication technologies.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

This initiative helped position WG 6 as an essential platform at the crossroads of AI and linguistic standardization. It supported Europe’s role in leading the development of value-driven digital standards aligned with ethical principles, interoperability needs, and the goal of a multilingual digital space.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

My project is directly leading to the development of new standardization content. As Convenor of ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6, I coordinate the development of ISO/AWI TR 25896, a new Technical Report titled “AI for Terminology Management.”

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I am driving efforts to identify and propose new standards, including initiatives like “Terminology Management for AI,” to address emerging needs at the intersection of language and artificial intelligence.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/48136.html>

Enhancing AI Risk Management and QMS Standards for EU AI Act regulatory purposes in CEN/CENELEC

Aleksandr Tiulkanov

*EU AI Act Trainer, AI Governance Consultant, Responsible Innovations
France*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence Working Group 2
Operational Aspects

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship, I am engaged to CEN/CENELEC AI Risk Management and QMS standards projects where I am supporting the consideration of the needs and resource constraints of SMEs. I am cooperating with other workgroup members to find appropriate solutions.

Hence, the priority is to ensure the closure of the above gap, plus facilitating consensus-building by submitting proposals and voicing real-time discussion comments that aim to bridge diverging contributions.

Moreover, the most significant challenged that we have overcome in this activity, is divergence between the positions of fundamental rights- and consumer protection-focused organisations, on the one hand, and business-minded stakeholders, on the other hand. Each group has legitimate concerns over the content, but the proposed solutions are often mutually exclusive.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I am contributing to prEN 18228 (JT021024) AI Risk Management and prEN XXX (JT021039) Artificial intelligence - Quality management system for EU AI Act regulatory purposes. Both standards are developed by CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG2.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This activity has significant impacts on AI standardization and European interests, notably related to the facilitated EU AI Act Compliance, as there will be a more clear alignment between standards and regulatory requirements will simplify compliance processes for organizations. Also, this allows reduced compliance costs and efforts, particularly beneficial for SMEs and startups in the AI sector.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing to the development of two new AI standards at CEN/CENELEC, listed here above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The project includes participation in online working group meetings and two face-to-face meetings, and I continue collaborating with experts from across Europe to build consensus on these critical standards. The resulting standards will provide organizations with practical tools to ensure their AI systems are safe, trustworthy, and compliant with European regulations, ultimately supporting Europe's vision of human-centric AI.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2916257&cs=11D701467243B7C63DEF4702C86E0138A

Taking the Micro-SME Voice into Securing Artificial Intelligence (SAI) Standardization Activities

Sandra Feliciano

Founder and CEO, AESTAS INSIGNIS - Investigação e Suportes de Apoio à Gestão, Unipessoal, Lda.

Portugal

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI Technical Committee on Securing Artificial Intelligence (ETSI TC SAI)

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship addresses three key aspects: a representation gap in standardization, the Foundational Driver of Cybersecurity, and the societal challenge of embedding European values into ICT standards.

There is a persistent lack of SME and Micro-SME representation in the development of AI and cybersecurity standards. ETSI TC SAI, like many ICT-focused committees, is primarily shaped by large multinational corporations, often overlooking the practical constraints and implementation realities of smaller European actors. This gap compromises the inclusiveness and overall applicability of standards.

I contribute to the Cybersecurity/Network and Information Security priority under the Key Enablers and Security policy area of the ICT Rolling Plan. It targets security-by-design practices in AI systems and promotes flexible, risk-based guidance suitable for smaller organizations. It also supports the Artificial Intelligence priority by influencing standards that govern safe and trustworthy AI deployment.

Moreover, ensuring that ICT standards reflect core European values such as transparency, accountability, and digital dignity is challenging. These are at risk when standardization is dominated by large actors. At the same time, standards must comply with WTO TBT principles like openness, impartiality, relevance, and consensus. If not properly safeguarded, both values and principles may be undermined. This project is addressing these risks by promoting inclusive participation, aligning standards with EU policy, and ensuring they are practical and accessible for SMEs and Micro-SMEs.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship strengthens the ICT Standards landscape by amplifying the representation of European SMEs and Micro-SMEs within ETSI TC SAI, as well as female voices in ICT. By participating in drafting and reviewing deliverables, I ensure that standards reflect both the technical needs and the operational constraints of smaller organizations, which are often overlooked in a landscape dominated by large multinationals.

The work is notably focused on TS 104 158-1 (AI Common Incident Expression – AICIE).

These deliverables aim to harmonize incident reporting, improve risk management, and mitigate harm from emerging AI threats. By ensuring that these outputs consider the needs of diverse stakeholders, this project supports a more inclusive and resilient ICT standards landscape at both European and international levels.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This contribution helps ensure that cybersecurity and AI standards are usable and relevant for SMEs and Micro-SMEs, which often lack the capacity to influence or implement complex requirements. By representing their needs in ETSI TC SAI, I promote practical, inclusive solutions that reflect operational realities.

Impact on Society

The work also impacts European society by aligning standards with EU values such as transparency, accountability, and digital dignity. It supports safer, more trustworthy AI systems while reinforcing policy objectives in the AI Act and Cyber Resilience Act. This enables broader adoption and public trust.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not directly yet, as I became an official member of ETSI in June 2025, and I started to contribute to the ongoing key projects of ETSI TC SAI from this moment onward.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I will continue to work on TS 104 158-1 (AICIE) until the next TC meeting in early September 2025, at ETSI headquarters in Sophia Antipolis.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.etsi.org/technologies/securing-artificial-intelligence

Support for activities as the Project Leader of the TR “AI for Terminology Management”

Mohamed Khemakhem

CEO, MandaNetwork

France

Sector

Data interoperability

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 37 SC 3 Management of terminology resources WG 6
Terminology Management and Artificial Intelligence

Role

Project leader and convener of ISO TC37 SC3 WG6

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With the support of this fellowship, I am drafting a Technical Report (TR) that addresses a critical gap between the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies and the structured, high-quality demands of terminology management. Currently, there is no unified framework that explains how AI can realistically and effectively augment terminological workflows. Many terminology professionals lack the technical understanding to evaluate AI tools, while AI developers often design systems without a deep understanding of terminological requirements. This disconnect results in underutilization of AI or misalignment between tools and professional needs.

The technical report prioritizes the creation of a task-based framework that maps core terminology tasks (e.g., corpus compilation, term extraction, concept relations) to the AI technologies best suited to support them. It also emphasizes dual-perspective guidance: enabling terminologists to better assess AI tools, and helping AI developers align their technologies with linguistic and conceptual accuracy. Another key priority is the inclusion of real-world use cases and quality benchmarks to support informed decision-making and promote responsible AI adoption.

Moreover, this technical report addresses several practical and ethical challenges, including data quality, domain-specific adaptability, lack of explainability in AI outcomes, and concerns about bias and ethical misuse. It also tackles the complexity and interconnection of terminology tasks, which are often treated in isolation by current tools. Additionally, the TR responds to the challenge of fragmentation by proposing future standardization pathways to support sustainable, scalable integration of AI in terminology management.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship contributes to the ICT standards landscape by developing structured, standards-aligned guidance on how artificial intelligence can effectively support and enhance terminology management tasks. By bridging domain-specific terminology practices with emerging AI capabilities—such as machine learning and natural language processing—the project promotes greater interoperability, scalability, and ethical implementation across multilingual and digital communication contexts.

It supports the evolution of ICT standards by addressing current gaps between AI tool development and structured language workflows, helping both terminologists and AI developers better understand and apply relevant standards. The ISO/AWI TR 25896 “AI for

Terminology Management” is being developed in direct alignment with several key ICT-related standards, which cover:

- ▷ ISO 1087:2019 defines the core vocabulary used in terminology work and terminology science.
- ▷ ISO/IEC 22989:2022 establishes standardized concepts and terminology related to Artificial Intelligence.
- ▷ ISO 12616-1:2021 provides guidelines for terminology work in support of multilingual communication.
- ▷ ISO 5078:2025 focuses on methods and best practices for terminology extraction.
- ▷ ISO 704:2022 outlines fundamental principles and methods for conducting terminology work.

Collectively, these standards provide the conceptual, methodological, and technological foundation for the TR, ensuring that its guidance reflects best practices from both the terminology and AI communities. This alignment not only strengthens current ICT standardization but also lays the groundwork for future collaborative developments at the intersection of AI and language technologies.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Yes, my contribution positively impacts both European SMEs and societies. The Technical Report ISO/AWI TR 25896 provides practical, standards-aligned guidance on integrating AI into terminology workflows, helping SMEs—especially in language services, translation, and AI—adopt advanced technologies efficiently and responsibly. It lowers technical barriers, supports scalability, and promotes competitiveness across multilingual markets.

Impact on Society

For European societies, the TR encourages trustworthy and ethical AI adoption by addressing issues like explainability, data quality, and inclusiveness. It supports transparency and linguistic accuracy in domains such as healthcare, public services, and education, aligning with core European values and fostering public trust in AI-driven tools.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

My project is directly leading to a specific proposal for the development of a new standardization document. The outcome of the project is the ISO/AWI TR 25896 “AI for Terminology Management”, currently under development within ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6. This TR builds on the foundational work of the Ad Hoc Group ISO/TC 37/SC 3/AHG1 transformed into ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WG 6 and provides structured guidance on the integration of AI into core terminology processes. It maps AI technologies to specific terminology tasks and ethical considerations, paving the way for future normative standards. Additionally, the TR identifies priority areas for further standardization—such as AI-based terminology evaluation and multilingual data governance—potentially informing future international standards or technical specifications.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Four task forces have been established to parallelize work across groups of terminology management tasks. Their goal is to define coherent scopes for the 12 identified tasks while addressing overlaps commonly found in real-world terminology workflows. The outcome of this stage will form the foundation for detailing the relevant AI applications for each task, as well as identifying associated limitations and risks.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/48136.html>

ISO 23042 - Decentralised identity management

Paolo Campegiani
Head of Innovation, Bit4id
Italy

Sector

Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and DLT /JWG4 Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG: Security, privacy and identity for Blockchain and DLT

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The European Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW) is a new trust service envisioned by Regulation 2024(1183) ("eIDAS2"). With the EUDIW, European citizens and companies will have a distributed identity management model to control their data, getting attributes about them (e.g. education) from an authorized source (e.g. a university) and be able to decide if and how to show them to a service provider (called a Relying Party in eIDAS2, e.g. a perspective employer). This model is specific to Europe, but the more general approach (often called self-sovereign identity) is being considered as the new way to provide digital identity to citizens in many countries of the world.

In this fellowship, I tackle the gap regarding the lack of a specific standard that deals with the interoperability of different wallets at the trust/semantic level. Such standard will leverage the consensual based nature of a distributed ledger. Moreover, the Rolling Plan ICT standardisation 2025³, includes a specific priority especially regarding Electronic Identification and trust services including e-signatures, in line with the new eIDAS Regulation.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I am dealing with ISO 23042 Reference architecture for DLT-based decentralized identity systems, as a project leader. This standard will provide a blockchain-based system to describe the trust framework of a decentralized identity system.

This document defines a reference architecture for DLT-based decentralized identity systems, which includes

- ▶ The lifecycle management of digital identities and associated attributes and credentials in a decentralized identity system including migration of individual digital identities into another system.
- ▶ The lifecycle management of the relevant actors and entities, including digital wallets, within a decentralized identity system.
- ▶ The use of trust anchors through a decentralized identity system.

³ <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2025>

▷ The entire lifecycle management of the decentralized identity system.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Europe is developing its decentralized identity system (European Digital Identity Wallet - EUDIW). Many companies and citizens in Europe will adopt EUDIW; therefore, a standard that supports interoperability will facilitate the use of credentials, stored in the wallet, outside of Europe.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am the project leader of a new standard in draft, ISO 23042 - Reference architecture for DLT-based decentralized identity systems

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The first working draft of the standard has been successfully developed, discussed and the disposition of comments was dealt, now we are now on second working draft. The TC/307 plenary will be held this Autumn 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html>

EUDIW components requirements and guidelines, according to the risk assessment

Raul Sanchez-Reillo

*Full Professor and R&D Group Director, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Spain*

Sector

Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/TC 224 Personal identification and related personal devices with secure element, systems, operations and privacy in a multi sectorial environment WG20 European Digital Identity Wallets

Role

Editor, Contributor and Co-convenor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Within the development of the future EUropean Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW), a group of risk management experts has been working in analysing the risks in terms of functionality, security and privacy.

That same group of experts has also realized that as different implementations of the EUDIW may co-exist, it will be very difficult to try to create single certification process, being much better to decompose the product in functional components, addressing the certification by components. This way, each implementation may decide their way to cover such components, and the certification body may be able to perform the relevant evaluations without considering a complete new product, reducing costs and time.

The work has been included into CEN TC224 WG20 workplan, but it has also been presented to other relevant groups, such as the DC CONNECT and ENISA's Ad-Hoc Working Group (AHWG) on Certification.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

When a sudden interest is created, there is a risk that both technological and standardization works will be developed in different lines, contradicting one to each other. Therefore, it is a must to coordinate all those efforts, trying to reach a common ground and reduce the workload and the risk of creating a non-usable product.

The work in this fellowship will take as the normative references the following documents:

- ▶ CEN/TR 17982:2023 “European Digital Identity Wallets standards Gap Analysis”
- ▶ prCEN/TS 18098 “Guidelines for the onboarding of user personal identification data within European Digital Identity Wallets”
- ▶ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17 AG3 Annual Reports
- ▶ ISO/IEC 18013-5 “Personal identification — ISO-compliant driving licence — Part 5: Mobile driving licence (mDL) application”

- ▷ ISO/IEC TS 18013-7 “Personal identification — ISO-compliant driving licence — Part 7: Mobile driving licence (mDL) add-on functions”
- ▷ ISO/IEC 23220 series “Cards and security devices for personal identification — Building blocks for identity management via mobile devices”

And all documents generated by the European Commission about the eIDAS2 regulation, including the ARF and the forthcoming Implementing Acts.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

When the European Identity Wallet will be defined, all service providers will have to adapt their services to use that wallet. Most of services providers are either SMEs or use solutions developed by SMEs, so the definition of that identity wallet will have a major impact on the activities of those SMEs, increasing their workload, and therefore, their benefits.

Impact on Society

This activity paves the path to the technical definition and implementation of the EUDIW and the services related. It is important to note that by reaching interoperable EUDIWs, the following sectors will benefit:

- ▷ Service providers and Administrations will find their work easier in identifying the citizen using the service, without acquiring more information that the one really needed. Therefore, the accomplishment of GDPR policies will be easier.
- ▷ Manufacturers and integrators will have to go only through one set of specifications, not creating products that may not be accepted by the context of eIDAS2.
- ▷ Citizens will see their identity secured, and privacy enhanced by only disclosing the relevant information to the services being used.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The target of this proposal is to be able to develop two work items in CEN TC224 WG2, titled:

- ▷ Decomposition of the EUDI Wallet – Part 1: Decomposition of the Solution by Module in the objective of Functional and Security Certifications (WI=00224287)
- ▷ Decomposition of the EUDI Wallet – Part 2: Decomposition of the Provider by Service in the objective of Functional and Security Certifications (WI=00224286)

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Both work items are currently in WD4 stage, seeking WD5 by the end of September 2025, and hopefully being able to go for Formal Vote in Spring 2026.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6205&cs=1E59B4D3EFD280E27AAC0C16CC13CD4FD

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:3039983&cs=1ED73E81641C336D9941EBF0462D984C7

Advancing Thing Description 2.0: Enhancing Affordances and more for Complex IoT Interactions

Cristiano Aguzzi

*Lead Software Engineer, Archeion
Italy*

Sector

IoT Internet of Things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

W3C Web of Things WG and Autonomous Agents on the Web
Community Group

Role

Invited Expert

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship, I directly tackle gaps and challenges in the Web of Things (WoT) Thing Description (TD) 1.1, specifically its limited ability to represent complex device behaviors and facilitate AI-driven interactions. TD 1.1 currently struggles with describing asynchronous actions, such as a coffee machine queuing multiple brew requests, where the operation is not instantaneous but involves a delayed completion and possibly ongoing status updates. It also lacks mechanisms for precisely extracting relevant data from intricate protocol payloads, meaning TD designers can not selectively choose or map specific pieces of information from a complex data stream, instead forced to consume the entire payload or nothing. Furthermore, the standard falls short in explicitly defining relationships between different affordances, such as an action directly updating a property's state or triggering an event, leading to an incomplete and fragmented description of a device's true operational logic. These shortcomings inevitably lead to proprietary workarounds as developers seek to describe these complex interactions, thereby fragmenting the IoT ecosystem. Moreover, these limitations significantly impede AI agents from reliably interpreting and interacting with devices, posing a critical barrier for developing robust, autonomous systems that rely on semantic understanding of device capabilities.

In the first phase of this fellowship activity, I address these issues by collecting diverse real-world use cases and researching how different IoT platforms currently handle or diverge from the standard. This "user-centric" approach tries to solve pain points for users and developers, and may also find new interaction patterns that are currently overlooked by the existing standard.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This work contributes to the ICT Standards landscape by directly advancing the W3C Web of Things (WoT) standards, particularly the Thing Description (TD) next version. I focus on improving TD's ability to represent complex device behaviors and facilitate AI-driven interactions. I participate in the WoT Working Group and potentially collaborate with the Autonomous Agents on the Web Community Group, which will provide crucial feedback and practical requirements for standard development. A tangible outcome of this work will be

the publication of a working draft for the next Thing Description version, incorporating the new features and themes I develop during this program.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

By strengthening the Web of Things (WoT) and its Thing Description (TD) specification, the project empowers European enterprises, including SMEs, to develop more advanced, flexible, and scalable IoT solutions. This reduces their dependence on non-European proprietary ecosystems, fostering a more resilient digital economy within Europe. Furthermore, the refinements to TD's ability to model complex interactions facilitate seamless data exchange, which is helpful for initiatives like Digital Product Passports (DPPs). This directly supports European societies by enabling greater transparency and traceability in supply chains, aligning with sustainability goals.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. It is planned to publish a revised Working Draft for Thing Description next version. The exact version number is still in discussion.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The real contribution to the standard text will start once we have finalized and understood the requirements of the different topics described in this project. This involves still more discussion with stakeholders and possibly some implementation effort to test possible solutions.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.w3.org/community/webagents/

Request for funding for IETF IoT work

Maria Ines Robles

*IoT Researcher, Tampere University
Finland*

Sector

Internet of Things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IETF ROLL (Routing Over Low power and Lossy networks) Working Group
IETF IoT-Directorate
IETF Routing-Directorate
IETF General-Area Review Team

Role

Co-Chair of IETF ROLL Working Group (WG)

Co-chair of the IETF Internet of Things (IoT) Directorate

Member in other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The IETF ROLL Working Group (WG) addresses critical challenges in developing efficient and secure routing protocols, such as RPL, tailored for energy-constrained environments. These environments include low-power and lossy networks commonly found in smart cities and industrial IoT applications. A significant challenge is ensuring robust and reliable communication despite energy constraints and device failures. European industrial plants, in particular, face challenges in maintaining seamless connectivity and interoperability among wireless devices. RPL addresses these issues with features such as self-healing capabilities, which are essential for sustaining reliable operations in IoT applications within European smart industries.

The key priorities of the ROLL are to integrate energy-saving mechanisms that extend device lifetimes while maintaining reliable communication. By supporting diverse routing metrics, RPL can adapt to varied use cases. Additionally, RPL scalability ensures it can accommodate an increasing number of nodes without introducing network complexity, while its zero-touch configuration simplifies IoT device deployment and management.

Despite these strengths, RPL still faces gaps that require attention. These include improving support for secure network enrollment processes to protect against unauthorized access, extending modes of operation, and improving objective function. Addressing these gaps is critical to improving the reliability, and applicability of RPL across diverse IoT scenarios, particularly in European industrial and urban deployments.

Another priority is advancing collaboration and knowledge sharing across the IoT ecosystem. The IETF IoT Directorate bridges informational gaps and engages organizations less involved in IETF activities. By fostering collaboration and aligning with evolving IoT standards, this effort accelerates the adoption of best practices in IoT deployments and advances the broader ICT standards landscape.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The IETF develops globally recognized Internet protocols and recommendations. At the IETF, I serve as the co-chair of the ROLL (Routing Over Low-power and Lossy Networks) Working Group (WG), which focuses on developing advanced routing protocols essential for IoT applications, including Industry 4.0, smart healthcare systems, smart grids, intelligent homes, and urban smart cities. Our work enhances connectivity in low-power and lossy network environments, with a primary focus on refining protocols such as RPL (IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks) and MPL (Multicast Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks). These protocols are foundational to enabling secure, efficient, and scalable communication in IoT systems. Additionally, we prioritize routing security and the continued evolution of IPv6, aligning our efforts with the milestones set by the working group.

In my role as co-chair of the IETF IoT Directorate, I lead a team of experts in coordinating various IETF IoT groups working across diverse areas, such as routing, security, application layers, transport layers, and operations. My responsibilities include increasing the visibility of these groups, fostering collaboration with external Standards Development Organizations (SDOs), and harmonizing IoT-related efforts. This work ensures alignment with global standards and accelerates the dissemination and development of IoT standards.

Additionally, my involvement in the Routing Directorate as a reviewer focuses on improving the quality of IETF routing standards. Through my participation in the Gen-Area Review Team, I contribute to refining the overall quality of IETF standards and recommendations, ensuring they meet the highest standards of functionality and relevance. Together, these roles allow me to address critical gaps, enhance collaboration, and advance the ICT standards landscape through the development of robust, scalable, and secure Internet protocols.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The work of the IETF ROLL WG significantly impacts European SMEs by developing internationally recognized open standards, such as RPL. RPL presents multiple open-source implementations, has been tested through extensive simulations and continuous evaluations. Also, RPL meets all their required capabilities, such as energy-efficient mechanisms, which are pivotal for sustainable growth.

Moreover, the continuous enhancements by the ROLL WG are vital for the evolution and adaptation of new use cases pertinent to the European context. These improvements ensure robust interoperability and adherence to security standards, both of which are critical for SMEs operating in the dynamic European market. This commitment to excellence and relevance is applied in the standard reviews carried out within the IETF Directorates, such as IoT, Routing, and General-Area sectors. Such endeavors underscore our dedication to supporting the technological advancement and operational efficiency of European SMEs.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. The chairing of ROLL (Routing Over Low Power and Lossy Networks) at the IETF led to the development of the following standard work: Controlling Secure Network Enrollment in RPL networks (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); Mode of Operation extension (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); Common Ancestor Objective Function and Parent Set DAG Metric Container Extension (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); RPL Capabilities (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); Destination Information Solicitation (DIS) Modifications (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track).

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The work in progress involves chairing and contributing to the standardization of key enhancements for RPL (Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Networks), including Secure Network Enrollment, Extension of the Mode of Operation, Common Ancestor Objective Function and Parent Set DAG Metric Container Extension, RPL capabilities and DIS Modifications in RPL.

Additionally, I provide technical guidance, organize and chair meetings, and oversee the management of the ROLL WG. As the co-chair of the IETF IoT Directorate, I am coordinating work across various IETF working groups, engaging with directorate members, and maintaining active communication and collaboration with SDOs. I also continue as a reviewer for standard work in the Gen-Area Review Team and Routing Directorate, ensuring the quality and consistency of IETF proposals.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/roll/about/>

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/iotdir/about/>

Completing the next steps in CBOR and CDDL

Carsten Bormann

*Self-employed (Freiberufler), Universität Bremen, TZI
Germany*

Sector

IoT Internet of Things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IETF WG Concise Binary Object Representation Maintenance and Extensions (CBOR)

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Interchange of information for Internet of Things (IoT), in particular for security-critical information, is best based on a standardized data representation format. Existing data representation formats such as XML or JSON have generally focused on capable platforms and were designed before pervasive cryptographic processing yielded most of the data in binary form. The Concise Binary Object Representation (CBOR) was designed as the foundational data representation format for the IoT and, since its standardization 2013 and revision 2020, has also obtained a major role in concisely representing security-critical information even beyond IoT applications.

In the first decade of CBOR use, a number of areas became apparent where additional standardization was desirable. For instance, the Concise Data Definition Language (CDDL) was standardized in 2019 as a language to describe the structure of CBOR (or JSON) information, enabling tool use for validation and code generation, as well as usage for documentation and specification (i.e., the standards that ultimately use CBOR).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Four current IETF Internet-Drafts have been selected for this proposal, as they are technically complete and just need a final editorial push and the management of review comments in the coming process steps. Three of these drafts have received updates already as a result of the first half of this project, the fourth is set to receive a final formative update now.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The specifications being completed provide standardization infrastructure that will enable the development of (and increase the technical quality of) application standards that rely on data representation formats. Recent developments such as the European vaccination certificates or the ISO mobile driving license use CBOR and CDDL and can directly benefit from the completion of the activities described.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, this fellowship supports my contributions to the CBOR standards, including the following parts

1. draft-ietf-cbor-cde, CBOR Common Deterministic Encoding (CDE), picks up “deterministic encoding” as defined in Section 4.2 of RFC 8949, used only for a subset of applications of a data representation format, but is enabling for those. CDE is intended as a more accessible specification that makes these choices in a way that is practically universally applicable.
2. draft-ietf-cbor-packed, Packed CBOR, defines a compact format for CBOR data that reduces internal redundancies while staying as easy to process as any other CBOR data.
3. draft-ietf-cbor-edn-literals, CBOR Extended Diagnostic Notation (EDN), consolidates the definition of EDN, an ancillary text format to CBOR’s binary format facilitating diagnostics, development, and specification.
4. draft-ietf-cbor-cddl-modules, CDDL Module Structure, defines ways for CDDL specifications of CBOR data formats to export and import partial specifications.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The work on these four standardisation items is ongoing and now the focus is reviewing and editing all disposed comments to then produce the final versions.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/cbor/about/>

Quality of Service in IoT Architecture using the oneM2M Standard

Thierry Monteil
Professor, INSA Toulouse
France

Sector

Internet of Things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI smartM2M
oneM2M SDS
ETSI DATA

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Several gaps are identified in this project on oneM2M standard. The main one is a lack of runtime QoS Indicators (e.g., latency, throughput, message loss, availability). There is no mechanism for QoS Exposure at the application level in oneM2M Resource Model. There is no clear methodology for Integrating QoS Monitoring into oneM2M and a weak support for QoS-Aware Architectures (Edge/Fog/Distributed Systems). There is also a lack of awareness and tools for developers regarding QoS in oneM2M and in fact a limited standardization activity around application-Layer QoS with a mapping between QoS requirements and domain-specific use cases.

This fellowship focuses on the definition of standardization of runtime QoS indicators. First demonstrations in Open-Source oneM2M Stack will help for credibility of the project results with an open Access to source and documentation.

The challenges are to define universally acceptable QoS indicators and to express the dynamic QoS management capabilities and the complexity integration within oneM2M Architecture. The results should take care of the QoS context-sensitive and ensuring practicality and relevance of implementation with interoperability capabilities across stacks.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I contribute to several standardisation activities, including:

- ▶ Enhancing the oneM2M standard with runtime QoS Capabilities by proposing concrete mechanisms to define, measure, and expose QoS indicators within the oneM2M framework, addressing a critical gap at the middleware/application layer. I
- ▶ Driving Cross-Layer QoS Integration in ICT Standards with a first links of QoS management across network, edge, and application layers, offering a complete vision of service assurance in distributed IoT systems.
- ▶ Supporting ongoing standardization efforts at ETSI and oneM2M by promoting open, testable, and reproducible standards. It makes a bridge between research, industry, and standards on the topic of QoS.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

My activity focuses on the domain of the Internet of Things (IoT) and explores its application in various strategic sectors such as eHealth, Industry 4.0, Intelligent Transportation Systems, Smart Cities, and Smart Grids. These domains align with development priorities at the European level.

IoT technologies are increasingly being deployed in diverse and resource-constrained environments. Cost constraints are driving manufacturers to select hardware that delivers performance tailored to the specific requirements of each use case, particularly in large-scale public applications (e.g., energy systems and urban infrastructure). In this context, the ability to assess and guarantee Quality of Service (QoS) according to the intended system usage is becoming critical. While such mechanisms are being addressed at the network level in 5G—and are anticipated in 6G—QoS considerations remain largely unaddressed at higher software layers, particularly within IoT systems.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes; I contribute to revising an existing standard as this project aims to investigate the quality-of-service indicators that could be offered by the oneM2M standard during runtime.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

At the end of this fellowship, the first goal is to define and describe a set of indicators, explaining how they can be measured and accessed through oneM2M resource descriptions. We then plan to provide a simple code example to demonstrate the benefits and potential applications of these indicators. Finally, this study will engage with the oneM2M and ETSI consortia to discuss and advocate for the evolution of the oneM2M standard.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.etsi.org/committee/smartm2m

Future of UHF RFID radio regulations - meeting new requirements from the European Commission

Josef Preishuber-Pflügl

Owner, innobir e.U.

Austria

Sector

Internet of things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI ERM TG34 Radio Frequency Identification Devices (RFID)

Role

Chair

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship tackles the gap that occurred due to the unexpected change in the work leadership and the lack of experts from huge companies, and furthermore due to new requirements issues by the European Commission. Stepping in short-term is for the benefit of a continuous progress and shall bridge the gap to ensure that the important work is continued with the educated expert and that in future a different solution is found. The priority of my contribution is to address the news changes required by the European Commission. Hence, we must update the standard to allow the citation in the EU OJ despite the ongoing changing requirements.

The ongoing changing requirements are the key challenges, as requirements change faster then it is possible to react in the standardisation process.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The activity is the continuation of the ETSI ERM TG34 "RFID" work to serve the industry and the European Commission that required the harmonised standards (EN). These standards are in particular relevant for IoT and DPP. If DPP (digital product passport) would like to use the passive UHF RFID (RAIN RFID) technology for DPP, then this requires continuous maintenance of the respective radio regulations and improvements of the measurement methods and test standards to follow technological progress and new advanced requirements from the European commission, like before the change from R&TTE to RED and now the new requirements for receiver resilience.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

The resulting harmonised standard will benefit SMEs, other industry players and European societies through the availability of provide and use certified products according the RED. RFID (UHF RFID, RAIN RFID) is a major used technology for the supply chain and production to reduce overproduction and waste. Furthermore, it is a technology for the Digital Product Passport, which is strongly supported by the European Commission for sustainable product regulations.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to revising existing standards, as ETSI EN 302 208 needs to be revised to address the new requirements from the European Commission.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The drafting has been progressing and as next step a review and then first ballot are planned.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://portal.etsi.org/TB-SiteMap/ERM/ERM-ToR/ERMtg34-ToR>

Actively contribute to ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC38 and IEEE S2ESC to harmonize standards across observability

Ruth Lennon

Lecturer, Atlantic Technological University
Ireland

Sector

Cloud and Edge Computing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC38 Cloud computing and distributed platforms WG6
Data, interoperability and portability
IEEE Software & Systems Engineering Standards Committee (S2ESC)

Role

Convener of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC38 WG6

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The IEEE and the ISO have agreed on the importance of observability standardisation. The IEEE are working on observability, and reliability from the perspective of software development. The ISO SC38 through AG5 are working on evaluating the observability topic from the perspective of cloud and distributed computing. These are significantly different but interrelated making this transfer of knowledge helpful in the development of platforms created using coded formats. Interestingly, many of the existing standards that involve software development quality procedures have failed to include participation of systems experts. This can lead to a lack of understanding of how the standards can be applied in the creation of infrastructure as code. More interestingly still is the lack of awareness of how some standards should be tailored to enable use in embedded or specialised environments such as edge or quantum computing.

Standardization of quality management practices, monitoring and observability for data management in cloud computing and big data, is key to the prevention of unforeseen legal and ethical risks related to use of multisource data, data from the edge, and as used in AI applications.

SC 38s work on ISO/IEC AWI 20151 on Dataspace concepts and characteristics is essential for modern computing concepts. As convener it is my role to aid the discussion and the progress of the work. SC 38, one of JTC 1's systems integration entities (SIE), integrates cloud computing and distributed platforms paradigm across both the ISO and IEC.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I have actively contributed to the following standards:

- ▷ IEEE 2675-2 Observability
- ▷ ISO/IEC 19941 Interoperability and portability
- ▷ ISO/IEC CD Dataspace concepts and characteristics
- ▷ ISO/IEC CD 22123 Concepts and Terminology

- ▷ IEEE 2675-1 Systems Reliability Engineering
- ▷ IEEE 730-2014 IEEE Standard for Software Quality Assurance Processes

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This preliminary work item has been proposed so that we can separate out the concepts involved in observability. Observability can occur across cloud computing, multi-cloud, distributed platforms and other areas. From early discussions with national bodies on the proposed preliminary work item was created to ensure a clear separation between the standards that are anticipated to come out of the work. Work on dataspaces with the CEN/CENELEC JTC 25 group have also indicated a need for greater quality management which can be enhanced through the application of observability. With these potential work items delineated more clearly we can aid growing organizations to improve their quality management in a scalable manner. This is essential for companies expanding across a European or wider market.

Impact on Society

Europe needs to continue the harmonisation of standards across standards bodies in evolving areas such as software development for cloud hosted or cloud enabled technologies. The key areas of Cloud computing and distributed platforms, and software development are essential supports for dataspaces, data management in Big Data and AI.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

This work has progressed from a topic in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/AG 5 to be proposed for consideration at the plenary for a preliminary work item, with the proposed Title: Information technology — Cloud computing and distributed platforms — Observability.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This first step allowed information to be gathered and to determine interest for the idea across national bodies. Now this item has progressed to be proposed for a preliminary work item as it has been determined that the work can impact many areas. It is therefore important to determine what potential standards or reports will come out of the topic and the division of responsibilities across each work item. It is anticipated that the next plenary of the ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 will see proposals for specific standards including draft outlines.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/601355.html>

 <https://www.computer.org/volunteering/boards-and-committees/standards-activities/committees/s2esc>

3.

3. Innovation for the Digital Single Market

New Sustainability standards within DLT & Blockchain Use - development of DLT Sustainability standards

Paul Ferris

Technical Expert, European Distributed Computing Association
Greece

Sector

Blockchain

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies
ISO/TC 307/AG1 SBP Review Advisory Group
Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG: Security, privacy and identity for Blockchain and DLT
ISO/TC 307/AG 2 Liaison Advisory Group
ISO/TC 307/CAG 1 TC307 Chair's Advisory Group
ISO/TC 307/WG 5 Governance
ISO/TC 307/WG 6 Use cases
ISO/TC 68/JWG1: Digital Currencies
CEN/CLC/JTC 19/WG 01 "Decentralised identity management"
BSI/DLT/1 "Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology"

Role

Convenor in ISO/TC 307/AG 1 SBP Review Advisory Group and in ISO/TC 307/CAG 1 TC307 Chair's Advisory Group

Expert member in other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this activity, I contribute to the prioritised 'gap areas' where the lack of adequate DLT/Blockchain standards is slowing the formulation of government regulations and cross border agencies, or where ambiguity of language is causing confusion or slowing integration of distributed systems.

The immediate priorities are ISO/TC307 SBP mandates to focus on UN Sustainable Development Goals and ISO's own Strategy to 2030. New sections are mandated and to date this work has gathered 11 new contributions for the two areas that needed development. These contributions are now integrated into the ISO/TC307 SBP working draft.

This work program specifically supports integration (especially across borders) & regulations (again multi-jurisdictional in particular); both crucial to EU integration and efficient operations.

Also, I have contributed to the piloting of the new ISO Strategic Business Planning process, applying the new template and methodology. This is the first change for 25 years. This project mandates specific topic areas and mandates a focus on the UN Sustainable Development Goals and ISO's own Strategy to 2030, both new subjects of discussion and policy development in the TC. These will be approached in a way that reflects the EU's IT planning approach and strategy.

It is necessary that ISO/TC307 future planning encompasses a strong European perspective that brings (for instance) GDPR and eIDAS priorities to global and regional standards. The European Interoperability Framework has already been proposed as an organising model for the SBP. The urgent need for support of regulation by global standards is particularly keenly felt in the European, multilateral context. The EU has a particular interest in such standards and it will benefit from strong regulations based on Global standards incorporating European values and norms. The EU is the gold standard for this multi-lateral coordination.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowships enables me to contribute to the planning and development of a strategy and business plan for the ISO/TC307 Technical Committee.

The following blockchain and distributed ledger technologies standards are affected by this fellowship activity:

- ▷ ISO/CD TS 18126: Taxonomy and classification for smart contracts
- ▷ ISO/DIS 20435: A framework for representing physical assets using tokens
- ▷ ISO/WD 23042: Reference architecture for DLT-based decentralized identity systems
- ▷ ISO/CD TS 23353: Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Auditing guidelines
- ▷ ISO/CD TS 23516: Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology — Interoperability Framework
- ▷ ISO/CD PAS 24874: Guidebook on the Use of Smart Contracts in Contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals
- ▷ ISO/WD 24876: Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Privacy protection when involving trust anchors in DLT-based identity management
- ▷ ISO/WD TR 24878: New and emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases
- ▷ ISO/WD 24946: Requirements and guidance for improving, preserving, and assessing the privacy capability of DLT systems.
- ▷ ISO/WD 25126: Information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for distributed ledger services
- ▷ ISO/CD TR 25145: Overview of DLT- based collections and collections management
- ▷ ISO 15489-1:2016: Information and documentation — Records management — Part 1: Concepts and principles
- ▷ ISO/WD TR 24332 on authoritative records, records systems, and records management⁴
- ▷ ISO/AWI PAS 24874 on Use of Smart Contracts in Contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals⁵
- ▷ ISO/AWI TR 24878 on DLT/Blockchain Use Cases⁶

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

There are a confusing range of possibilities that SME's are unlikely to be equipped to assess without a set of dependant standards to guide them. The criteria for such decisions needs examination, the approach & comparative measurement needs standards to be effective. This project links the SMEs operating in the business arena and the standards development to support their operations. Sustainability standards often have conflicting objectives, a specific plan to develop appropriate standards to the benefit of the EU SMEs is very applicable guidance.

Impact on Society

The sustainable role of DLT is in its ability to bring multi-vendor, multi-agency and multi-

4 <https://www.iso.org/standard/78465.html>

5 <https://www.iso.org/standard/88312.html>

6 <https://www.iso.org/standard/88315.html>

domain groups of stakeholders together such as required to tackle greenwashing and mass data verification. The standards require in such diverse areas as fish-farm verification to the development of mass data processing in space (especially relevant to the increasing load from AI systems), has the potential to extract over 15% of current energy use from the global atmosphere. Radical, but attainable schemes like these need rapid standards development to enable their use, so that the impact can be made within years, not decades

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The purpose of this work is to headline the priorities and justification for new standards. As convenor of TC307/AG1 the aim of this work is to produce a viable strategy for the whole technical committee, and so impacts all standards in process or coming up for review. I shall be making specific recommendations to the technical committee chair regarding which standards require development priority and the scope of every proposed standard the TC considers.

Specifically, the new working draft of the SBP has two new sections on the SDG and Sustainability, and contains specific recommendations for three new standards projects to be launched by TC307, plus proposals to establish JWG with other ISO and CEN TCs working on Sustainability.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Specific sections on 'Sustainability' (with particular reference to the EU) and reports from the COP 29 and proposals to underpin this work by establishing joint working groups with other ISO and CEN Technical Committees. Worthwhile recording is the collaboration with the Technical Committees Chair in contributing and smoothing the process. The scope of the AG1 group has been published and is part of the new ISO pilot program for new Strategic Business Planning in ISO. Sustainability is mandated in this template and a half day of plenary time has been allocated to discuss SBP proposals to the TC.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html>

The challenge of rewarding human creativity in the AI era

Panos Kudumakis
Independent Consultant
United Kingdom

Sector

Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1 SC29 Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information WG03 MPEG Systems Smart Contracts for Media Subgroup

Role

Chair of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG03 MPEG Systems Smart Contracts for Media Subgroup & Head of UK Delegation of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29 (MPEG & JPEG)

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Copyright legislation has continuously evolved so that fair, timely and transparent revenues are returned to artists and rights holders, e.g., US Music Modernisation Act and EU Digital Single Market Copyright Directive. Meanwhile, several key artists and media companies have turned their hopes for resolving these issues to blockchain, e.g., Open Music initiative by Berklee ICE in US and Mycelia by Imogen Heap in UK.

The EC Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation (2025) also reveals that the most critical areas of blockchain standardisation for IPR management are interoperability, identity, and smart contracts.

In line, the recently published ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media has already enriched DLT environments with inference and reasoning capabilities inherently associated with ontologies bridging the interoperability gap towards a semantic media blockchain. This standard will greatly assist the media stakeholders in achieving effective interoperability for the exchange of verified contractual data between different DLTs. Such a process in turn will increase trust among stakeholders for sharing high-value data (e.g., music rights) in the ecosystem.

Moreover, work has been initiated on ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format with aim to provide the means (e.g., APIs) towards enabling a fairer marketplace for rights holders while rewarding human creativity in the AI era based on widely deployed MPEG technologies (e.g., audio-visual codecs, file formats, streaming protocols, and smart contracts) and non-MPEG technologies (e.g., DLTs, content and creator IDs). Such a decentralised media ecosystem has the potential to unlock the Semantic Web and in turn the creative economy; drive a shift of power in the media value chain (e.g., from the intermediaries to artists and rights holders); and facilitate greater fan interactivity and engagement, e.g., fans could be a partial owner of new works and even become creators of new derivative works.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The MPEG Systems Smart Contracts for Media Subgroup, that I chair, has already published ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media in Nov. 2022. The latter supported by rich semantic copyright models can be handy when data-based decisions need to be derived by evidence and logic, leading to new business models that can be efficiently deployed on decentralised digital media platforms.

With respect to the latter, an additional challenge has been identified, that is, the interoperability of such platforms beyond smart contracts. Thus, work has been initiated on ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format standard with scope to provide the means (e.g., APIs) towards enabling a fairer marketplace for rights holders - taking into consideration the latest AI regulatory developments - based on MPEG technologies (e.g., audio-visual codecs, file formats, streaming protocols, and smart contracts) and non-MPEG technologies (e.g., DLTs, content and creator IDs). Its components will include: 1) smart contracts and DLTs (e.g., ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media); 2) rights metadata management (e.g., ingestion and queries); 3) content and creator IDs (e.g., ISCC – Content Codes and ISNI – Name Identifier); and, 4) file formats and streaming protocols (e.g., Tech Emmy® award winning ISO/IEC 14496-12 ISO Base Media File Format and ISO/IEC 23009 Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP). The focus will be on ISO/BMFF derived and widely deployed ISO/IEC 23000-23 Interactive Music Application Format and ISO/IEC 23000-19 Common Media Application Format for decentralised music and video applications, respectively.

That is, while ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media has bridged the interoperability gap towards a semantic media blockchain, ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralized Media Rights Application Format building around DLT-agnostic ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media is envisaged to unlock both the Semantic Web and in turn the creative economy.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

EU Digital Single Market Copyright Directive aims to facilitate a fairer marketplace for rights holders. Effective IP rights management in the digital environment is key to support the competitiveness of creative SMEs. ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media supported by rich semantic copyright models can be handy when data-based decisions need to be derived by evidence and logic, leading to new business models that can be efficiently deployed on decentralised digital media platforms. Moreover, the interoperability of such platforms is addressed by ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format which building around DLT-agnostic ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media has the potential to unlock the Semantic Web and in turn the creative economy. The latter is not only one of the most rapidly growing sectors of the world economy, but also a highly transformative one in terms of income-generation, job creation, export earnings, quality of life and social cohesion.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to both to a revised and to a new standard. This project, towards enabling a fairer marketplace for rights holders and remuneration of authors and performers while rewarding human creativity in the AI era, initiated work on a new standard ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format .

In addition, A revised standard ISO/IEC 21000-3 Digital Item Identification (2nd Edition) has also been produced consolidating its two amendments and leaving out the associated registration authority to the discretion of stakeholders.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The revised standard ISO/IEC 21000-3 Digital Item Identification (2nd Edition) is expected to be published as an International Standard (IS) in Aug. 2025. ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format which is currently at Working Draft (WD)

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45316.html

 <https://www.iso.org/standard/89735.html>

Mapping and Structuring the Standardisation Landscape of Virtual Worlds

Christoph Runde

*Managing director, Virtual Dimension Center (VDC) w.V.
Germany*

Sector

Virtual worlds

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

DIN NA 043-01-24 AA „Metaverse and Extended Reality“
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 24 “Computer graphics, image processing and
environmental data representation“
Metaverse Standards Forum WG “Metaverse Standards Register”
working group”

Role

Chair of DIN “eXtended Reality and Metaverse” group

Co-chair of Metaverse Standards Forum “Standards Registry” group

Member of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC24

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In the context of virtual worlds, the developer community uses far fewer standards than it could. Furthermore, the participation of large sections of the developer community (especially SMEs) in standardization work remains below potential. The biggest gap here is the lack of transparency in a highly fragmented standardization landscape comprising over 100 organizations, over 300 working groups, and over 1,000 standards.

My fellowships focuses on making the virtual worlds standards register accessible to a wide audience via the EUOS Standards Repository (the European Observatory for ICT Standardization (EUOS))⁷ created and and maintained by StandICT.eu. Currently, this repository contains few standards relating to virtual worlds.

The main challenges of this activity are to adapt the above-mentioned database to the requirements of DIN/ISO and the EUOS platform (categorization of subject areas and entries (e.g., standards, specifications, white papers, recommendations, working groups, SDOs, etc.) and preparing it for import for easy access (organizing, structuring, new tagging based on the new categories). Since standardization is a dynamic field of work, an update must first be carried out (research on topics and organizations).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship supports the European Commission’s efforts to introduce the virtual worlds community to the use of standards and active standardization work. The EU-funded ViWISSO project⁸ is currently underway, which aims, among other things, to qualitatively map the virtual worlds standards landscape. A complete, quantitative mapping and the creation of a database are not part of the project. However, this project will provide a useful addition here.

⁷ <https://www.standict.eu/euos>

⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/viwissoproject/>

The new European partnership “Virtual Worlds” will start in 2025. One of its strategic pillars is standardization, among other things to promote Europe’s digital sovereignty in this key technology. This project will also make a unique and critically important contribution to this.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The metaverse and eXtended Reality market is characterised by an intense battle for technological ecosystems. American companies dominate the XR platforms for desktop and handheld XR; VR headsets come from the USA, Taiwan or China; game consoles come from Japan or the USA. In Europe, there are many software manufacturers and a few hardware manufacturers. For suitable market access, standardisation is absolutely critical to digital sovereignty and strategic autonomy, and finally to the success of Europe’s SMEs.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No. My fellowship activity will not make any specific recommendations or proposals for new or revised standards, but will merely provide the basis for identifying them.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I have agreed to chair the technical working group of [StandICT.eu](https://standict.eu) dedicated to establishing a landscape analysis for virtual world standards. The group starts working in Fall 2025 and it will deliver a landscape analysis report that will be openly accessible for all interested stakeholders.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.standict.eu/euos

 <https://www.din.de/de/mitwirken/normenausschuesse/nia/nationale-gremien/wdc-grem:din21:374837076>

IEEE SA HyperSpatial Transaction Protocol Spec Editor and Leadership (co-chair) of IEEE P2874 WG

Christine Perey

*Independent Consultant, PEREY Research & Consulting
Switzerland*

Sector

Web 4.0 and virtual worlds

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE 2874 Working Group Spatial Web, Architecture and Governance Working Group

Role

Co-Chair

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship project is addressing a critical gap in the implementation of the 2874 Spatial Web standard. Specifically, the Spatial Web standard is a conceptual model and architecture, defining governance and scope of the Spatial Web. However, the actual transaction protocol whose requirements are defined in IEEE WG 2874, is being developed in collaboration with the engineers of the Spatial Web Foundation. The specification is being written in tandem with the HyperSpatial Modeling Language (HSML) that defines the ontologies that the HSTP uses.

Our priority is on the definition of the HSML and HSTP in coordination with the Universal Domain Graph (UDG), also described in the IEEE 2874 specification. The UDG's high level principles (how the UDG works and how to participate in it) are described in IEEE 2874, and now are being brought into focus and higher precision through collaboration with IoT engineers and experts.

The primary challenge we are encountering is the lack of implementation experience in these very complex topics. There have been many attempts to define a semantic data ontology schema for describing all objects, relations, and actions in the world in a standardized way. This editor is working with a team of ten engineers. Some of the team members have standards experience but most are new to standardisation.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This project is developing three ICT standards that are all tied together by requirements defined in the IEEE 2874 specification. The IEEE 2874 Working Group is developing the HyperSpatial Transaction Protocol (HSTP), HyperSpatial Modeling Language (HSML) and the Universal Domain Graph (UDG). Together these standards provide the protocols and semantics for the Spatial Web.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

HSTP shall be interoperable with IoT systems in such a way that the entities are able to exchange information and mutually use the information in an efficient way consistent with IEEE 2413 Architectural Framework for IoT.

Many innovative European SMEs, and companies that use IoT will benefit from the adoption of HSTP because it will remove the need to create an entirely proprietary protocol for the transaction of systems. HSTP shall provide interoperability of observations coming from physical sensors. It will also enable machine learning operations on sensor data, i.e., observations and measurements, accessible in the Spatial Web. HSTP will use the HyperSpatial Modeling Language (HSML), a human- and machine-readable modeling language and semantic data ontology schema that describes objects, relations, actions, activities and their permissions.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to two new standards: IEEE 2874 Working Group HyperSpatial Transaction Protocol (HSTP) and HyperSpatial Modeling Language (HSML)

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The specifications are under development. Due to the fact that HSTP will use the HyperSpatial Modeling Language (HSML), a human- and machine-readable modeling language and semantic data ontology schema that describes objects, relations, actions, activities and their permissions, we are developing the two specifications in parallel. Also, in parallel, implementations of samples of the protocol are under development for testing. This aids in reducing risk of a specification that is not fit for purpose.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://sagroups.ieee.org/2874/>

4. Sustainable Growth

Harmonizing Digital Product Passports and Circular Business Models

Julian Lauten-Weiss

*Deputy Chair of the Circular Economy Committee at the German Institute for Standardization (DIN), Bergische Universität Wuppertal
Germany*

Sector

Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

DIN/NA 172-00-20 AA “Circular Economy”
CEN/TC 473 WG 2 “Information Sharing” & WG 4 “Circular Business Models”
ISO/TC 323 “Circular Economy”

Role

Deputy chair of DIN/NA 172-00-20 AA “Circular Economy” and a member in the other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

There is a lack of harmonization between CEN/TC 473 WG 2 on information sharing and WG 4 on business models. The former deals with relevant parameters for digital product passports (DPPs) such as a common data dictionary, while the latter provides guidance on the implementation of ISO 59010 in a European policy context. As the only expert who is active in both working groups, I was able to use my unique position to address the identified gap by ensuring the consideration of terms from ISO 59010 in WG 2 as well as the consideration of DPPs in the guidance under development in CEN/TC 473 WG 4.

During this fellowship, the main priority became setting the agenda for CEN/TC 473 WG 4 to ensure conformity of the guidance under development with CEN/TC 473 WG 2 and EU directives and regulations such as the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), and Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). All of these documents emphasize the relevance of information sharing, necessitating a strong link between the DPP and business model elements.

During this fellowship, the central challenge was the low participation rate in CEN/TC 473 WG 4. Potential reasons could be a lack of experience with circular business models among standardisation experts, as well as the horizontal nature of this standard, lowering its perceived relevance for organisations that specialise in particular sectors or industries. This situation necessitated accelerating the drafting process while involving as many experts as possible to ensure a diverse range of perspectives.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

All circular economy standards are related to ICT. On the one hand, circularity is often enabled by ICT, such as DPPs. Comprehensive and interoperable DPPs are essential for a circular economy, as information on the composition of products and their parts must be transmitted throughout all use and life cycles. In the last few months, CEN/TC 473 WG 2 has discussed definitions of relevant terms collected during a previous work period funded by

StandICT. These terms will form a standard data dictionary in the document currently listed as WI 00473003.

On the other hand, circular business models are a promising approach to addressing e-waste, one of the fastest-growing waste streams globally (<https://ewastemonitor.info/>). CEN/TC 473 WG 4 has been working on aligning ISO 59010 more closely with European policies and regulations that frequently highlight ICT as one of the first sectors to move towards greater circularity. In the process of developing guidance on circular business models, ICT and in particular the DPP was considered at each step in the development of the document currently listed as WI 00473001.

This fellowship enabled me to contribute my expertise on ICT and circular business models and to harmonise guidance in WI 00473001 and WI 00473003 through agenda setting and active discussions in working groups.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

In particular, SMEs often lack sufficient funds to develop the internal capabilities necessary for transitioning to circular business models. Harmonizing the work in CEN/TC WG 2 and WG 4 and ensuring compatibility with European policies and regulations makes it easier to not just fulfil legal requirements but to also go beyond short-term requirements and gain a competitive advantage by transitioning to circular business models.

Impact on Society

Transitioning to a circular economy has profound societal impacts by promoting sustainability, resource efficiency, and economic resilience. It promotes a reduction in waste and pollution, thereby enhancing environmental quality and public health. Encouraging businesses to design for longevity, repairability, and recyclability creates new job opportunities and stimulates innovation across industries. Additionally, it empowers communities to adopt sustainable practices and reduces their dependency on finite resources. Overall, a circular economy nurtures a more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient society, aligning economic activities with long-term environmental and social well-being.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. The additional guidance being developed in CEN/TC WG 4 is intended to support the planned revision of ISO 59010 Circular economy — Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

As the work is still ongoing and has recently been extended, the exact publication dates of the documents are not yet precise. However, WI 00473001 should be completed and submitted by mid-2026 and WI 00473003 before the end of 2027.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.din.de/en/getting-involved/standards-committees/nagus/national-committees/68244/wdc-grem:din21:301803096!search-grem-details?masking=true

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:3326686&cs=1FB6C33369B0F6BEA8BA7EFC7B26D4309

<https://www.iso.org/committee/7203984.html>

Semiconductor and trusted chips landscape and gap analysis

Karim Tobich

*Director, CyberSecurity & Technology Consultancy Ltd
United Kingdom*

Sector

Digitisation of European Industry

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

StandICT.eu TWG Semiconductor and chips

Role

Co-chair of StandICT.eu TWG Semiconductor and chips

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship enabled me to cochair StandICT.eu TWG Semiconductor and chips. In this working group, the gaps that we are addressing through are related to the development of international standards related to semiconductors and chips. In this sense, the main objective of my fellowship is to co-chair the technical working group on Semiconductors and Chip Standardisation, provide contributions to the generation of a landscape overview and create a gap analysis. This will result to a comprehensive landscape and gap analysis report published as part of the [StandICT.eu](https://standict.eu) programme.

This project is monitored closely by the European Commission due to its strategic implication for the autonomy of the European community and for building and reinforcing strategic partnership when it comes to semiconductors and chips.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

So far the ICT Standards landscape that we analysed through this study covers more than 75 committees among them. The work performed through this contribution identified different standard development organisations (SDOs) and their relevant working groups covering different sectors of applications, and different technologies. This led to the creation of a list, based on the collection of almost 5,000 standards that has been prepared and classified into four main types of categories:

- ▷ applications,
- ▷ modules, or components,
- ▷ process steps, and
- ▷ relevance of those standards to semiconductor and chip technologies.

Finally, from the list of standards and their classifications, a landscape analysis was performed based on statistical and mathematical functions, and a gap was drawn and a report was written.

We aim that this report will be used and studied by the European Commission and the different SDOs. This will contribute among other reports to draw a roadmap for future investment and future standards that will contribute to the European Union economy.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Semiconductor and chip technologies are usually defined and created by large organizations. Nevertheless, European SMEs can be also impacted as those are usually the incubators for new technologies before expanding or getting bought by large organizations.

Impact on Society

The fellowship enables meeting the European strategy on Chips act and bolster Europe's competitiveness and resilience in semiconductor technologies and applications, and help achieve both the digital and green transition. In addition it allows for increased convergence of standardisation makers' efforts achieving EU policy goals by providing a common standard when it comes to EU and international SDO and reducing time for adoption. Developing and providing such standards to organisations allow them to implement the EU values and policies in an easy manner

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not directly. The work performed through this project highlighted different proposals and areas for standardisation. Nevertheless, the decision to create new standards does not belong to the TWG but to the SDOs and their members. We aim that the report provides an incentive for future collaboration.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The Technical working group (TWG) has finished this round of assessment covering landscapes and gap analysis in standards related to semiconductor and chip technologies within the timeframe allocated to this project. Nevertheless, technical working should be convened in a couple of years to assess the progress with regard to advancement in technology and innovation as this may lead to the need for new standards.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.standict.eu/landscape-analysis-reports

Guidance on digitalisation and management of data in the maintenance of assets

Daniel Gaspar

*Researcher and Professor, the Viseu School of Management Technology
Portugal*

Sector

Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/TC319 - Maintenance

Role

Convenor in ISO/TC 251 Asset Management WG8 – “People involvement and competence”
Member in other group

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The introduction of models and frameworks of data maintenance management makes it easier to deploy industry best practices, such as more sustainable operations and takes advantage with respect to the evolution observed nowadays.

With this fellowship, the priority is to propose a NWIP document within CEN/TC 319 on data management in industrial maintenance, taking advantage of the potential of the digitalization of the industry and new tools such as AI, ML, digital-twin, etc...

The challenge is to prepare a document that contains, in a reduced form, the topics, the frameworks and guidelines in the digital area of maintenance.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This activity is related to the following existing standards:

- ▷ ISO/IEC 42001:2023 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Management system.
- ▷ ISO/IEC 23053:2022 - Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML)
- ▷ ISO 14224 - Petroleum, petrochemical and natural gas industries — Collection and exchange of reliability and maintenance data for equipment

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

With this work, we'll provide some valuable tools that will enable industrial companies to better utilize their assets, giving them a competitive advantage. In a Europe committed to sustainability and digitalization, the introduction of models and frameworks of data maintenance management makes it easier to deploy industry best practices, such as more sustainable operations and takes advantage of value-based and intelligent asset management in order to make a step forward with respect to the evolution observed nowadays.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing to the development of a new standard, this envisaged NWIP is entitled "Guidance and frameworks on data and digital Maintenance Management".

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The first draft document is nearly finished and ready for a meeting with interested experts in September. Hopefully, at the TC319 plenary session, we can open a NWIP. So far, the opinions of several experts on the subject/first document have been very positive, providing further motivation to move forward with the process.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6300&cs=ICEF1EA360BD3851719B096E5D80D730A

Named address spaces for C

Philipp Krause

*Programmer, Researcher, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg
Germany*

Sector

ICT Environmental impact

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JCT1/SC22 Programming languages, their environments and system software interfaces WG14 C

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Many small microcontrollers have a heterogeneous memory architecture, which can be exposed in C by named address spaces, which are described in ISO/IEC TR 18037:2008 (i.e. outside the main C standard). Named address spaces are the only part of ISO/IEC TR 18037:2008 that is widely used. They should be brought into the main C standard to ensure that the impact of any future changes to the C standard on them is sufficiently considered (in particular named address spaces are implemented via C qualifiers, but have certain requirements that do not apply to other qualifiers, so making changes to qualifiers in the C standard can break named address spaces, and some such changes have already been proposed for the upcoming revision of the C standard). Furthermore, I read other proposals, in particular wrt. to their impact on small embedded devices. Often extra effort is required to ensure that conflicting goals (e.g. safety or security vs. energy or resource efficiency) can be balanced in a way suitable for these devices.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This work is mostly about getting a part of ISO/IEC TR 18037:2008 into ISO/IEC 9899 - Programming languages - C. By further standardizing the way named address spaces are exposed in the C programming language, we improve portability of user code between C implementations, which helps reduce vendor lock-in and makes Free/Open Source C implementations for small embedded systems more competitive vs. the entrenched Keil C-implementation from outside the EU.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Many SMEs use embedded systems programmed in C in their products. The activity will help ensure that the C standard can be efficiently implemented and does not hinder optimizations. This is particularly relevant both to high-performance computing (due to their performance requirements and high energy use) and to small systems (due to their resource and energy constraints and large number). This will result in reduced resource (memory, energy, computation time, money) usage in small and big systems, and thus in particular help lower the environmental footprint of IoT, sensor networks as well as high-performance computing.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the revision of an existing standard, including named address spaces in the next revision of ISO/IEC 9899 - Programming languages - C.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I have researched the current state of named address spaces in C implementations, and based on that made a proposal to include a part of ISO/IEC TR 18037:2008 into ISO/IEC 9899 - Programming languages - C, published as N3651⁹. However, there was an unusually high number of papers submitted for the upcoming Brno meeting. While my proposal has been discussed on the internal mailing list of SC22/WG14, it is currently on the preliminary Brno agenda as an item to be discussed if time permits only, otherwise discussion will be postponed to the next meeting (February 2026, virtual).

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.open-std.org/jtc1/sc22/wg14/>

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45202.html>

9 <https://www.open-std.org/jtc1/sc22/wg14/www/docs/n3651.pdf>

Virtual Worlds, 6G, Ethics and AI for Robotics and Autonomous Systems Standards

Paulo Gonçalves

*Professor, Instituto Politecnico de Castelo Branco
Portugal*

Sector

Robotics and autonomous systems

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE WG P1872.3 - Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots;

IEEE WG P3140.2 - Semantic Maps for Autonomous Robots - Part 2: Framework and Application Development Interface.

IEEE WG P1955 - Standard for 6G Empowering Robotics: Use Case Scenarios, Requirements, Architectural Impact, and Technical Assumptions

Role

Chair working group of IEEE P1872.3 “Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots”

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Four essential challenges were identified to be worked as part of my fellowship contributions:

- ▶ A foundational ontology of concepts that supports the effective selection and deployment of AI methods in multi-robot scenarios,
- ▶ Communication requirements for multi-robot systems leveraging 6G capabilities, within the context of elderly care applications, while incorporating relevant ethical considerations
- ▶ Formalize a core set of ontological elements necessary for the creation and use of semantic maps in robotic systems,
- ▶ A standardized set of ontological concepts that enable seamless interoperability between real-world robotic systems and their counterparts in virtual environments, such as digital twins.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my contributions for the ICT standards landscape within several domains, including: Robotics and Autonomous Systems, AI, interoperability, 6G. The focus will be on defining:

- ▶ a standardized way to express in a formal way, using ontologies, the existing AI methods that are used in the robotics domain,
- ▶ an ontological framework that enhances the interoperability between real robots and virtual worlds,
- ▶ a set of robotic requirements for the implementation of 6G in an healthcare use case, where robots at nursing homes interact with elderly.

I am dealing with standards related to robotics, namely the ones focused on knowledge representation, multiple robots, semantic maps. Lastly this project is also focused on defining the requirements for 6G to enhance robotic applications, e.g., ethics in older adult's care.

As the main effort, this activity aims to develop work towards standardization using ontologies (within WGs 1955, 1872.3 and lastly the 3140.2 on semantic maps) in several robotic sub- domains, covering: 6G to empower robots, machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms applied to robotics, and interoperability between real-world robotic systems and their counterparts in virtual environments, such as digital twins.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The contributions will make significant impact for the description of the robotics requirements on a healthcare scenario, where robots and humans operate. This will impact robot communication services that will use 6G.

Moreover, the fellowship strongly focuses on ontologies, to achieve a better interoperability of concepts to enhance robot to robot and robot to humans' communications. The use of the standardizes DOLCE upper ontology makes a significant difference.

Also, EU have within its borders numerous renowned robotics companies. An increasing number of cutting-edge robotics and autonomous systems now rely on AI-driven reasoning to handle their growing complexity. Today, global regulations are shaping how knowledge is represented for robotics services and tasks, and EU SMEs must comply with these standards. As a result, these knowledge representation standards will significantly influence the development of future robotic and autonomous systems.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. My work focuses on three new standards:

- ▷ IEEE WG 1872.3 - Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots; To develop a standardized way to perform ontological reasoning on multiple robots
- ▷ IEEE WG P3140.2 - Semantic Maps for Autonomous Robots - Part 2: Framework and Application Development Interface.
- ▷ IEEE WG P1955 - Standard for 6G Empowering Robotics: Use Case Scenarios, Requirements, Architectural Impact, and Technical Assumptions

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This fellowship is working towards three key outcomes at the end of this fellowship, in October 2025, including sets of:

- ▷ Ontological concepts for the proper selection and use of AI in multiple robots' scenario.
- ▷ Ontological concepts for semantic maps in robotic applications and for interoperability between virtual worlds (digital twins) and real robotic systems.
- ▷ Communication requirements for multiple robots' systems using 6G features within a specific use case in elderly care, considering ethical requirements.

Online references related to the fellowship work

📄 <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037/>

📄 <https://2025.ieee-rtsi.org/workshop-exploring-ethical-challenges-in-6g-iot-robotics-pathways-to-innovation/>

Robotics — Electrical interfaces — Connectivity interoperability for End-effectors

Morten Kühnrich

*Responsible for compliance and senior software developer,
4XRobots
Denmark*

Sector

Robotics and autonomous systems

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO TC299/WG9 Electrical interfaces for industrial robot end-effectors

Role

convenor of ISO/TC 299/WG9

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my role as a convenor of ISO/TC 299/WG9. We are working through committee comments on the first committee draft (CD1) of ISO 24112 “Robotics — Electrical interfaces — Connectivity and interoperability for end-effectors”

There is currently no global agreement on standardized electrical protocols and connectors for robotic end-effector equipment. Existing solutions are often region-specific or vendor-specific, which limits interoperability and hinders the adoption of modular robotic tooling on a global scale.

Our main priority is to align viewpoints so that robot end-effectors follow a standard for connector / protocols that is accepted and usable beyond Europe. This includes engaging with major robotic nations to build consensus and promote compatibility across markets.

The main challenge is reconciling different regional practices and industrial preferences for electrical protocols and connector designs. Achieving harmonization requires balancing technical requirements, legacy systems, and commercial interests, while ensuring safety and scalability for future robotic applications

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship contributes to the ICT Standards landscape by solidifying a European footprint on interoperability requirements for robotic end-effector equipment.

The ICT Standards we are dealing with are sustainable growth within robotics and autonomous systems, and data interoperability as a key enabler.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The current development of ISO 24112 “Robotics — Electrical interfaces — Connectivity and interoperability for end-effectors” happens with a strong European footprint. It will help European based companies to be competitive in a automation market that relies more and more on easy integration of plug-and-play automation products.

There are new market possibilities in delivering new ISO 24112 compliant products for a market

place that includes the inner market but also an international market. Furthermore access to ISO 24112 compliant products will help European robot and automation integrators to solve automation problems faster and hence accelerate the use of automation in Europe.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, this fellowship supports my contributions to the development of a new standard, ISO/AWI 24112 Robotics — Electrical interfaces — Connectivity and interoperability for end-effectors.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

It will be difficult to reach the DIS phase by the end of the year as first anticipated. Rather a comitee draft 2 will be within reach.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/standard/77833.html>

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/5915511.html>

Standardization in Robotics and AI for Healthcare

João Manuel Leitão Quintas

*RTD coordinator, Instituto Pedro Nunes
Portugal*

Sector

Robotics and autonomous systems

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE SA P 1872.3 REMAR - Ontology for reasoning on multiple autonomous robots
IEEE SA P1872.2 Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology Working Group

Role

Secretary

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship aims to contribute to ongoing efforts related to standardisation and European policy advising on topics mainly related to Robotics and Autonomous Systems and Artificial Intelligence.

The key objective of the proposed activity is to contribute to the discussions and creation of resources that can support and facilitate the dissemination and adoption of standards, policy and guidelines proposed by key opinion leaders involved mainly in the recently created Working Group that is developing the standard project IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots.

In the current state of the art, the implementation of standard ontologies in Robotics and Autonomous Systems is still considered a challenge, but is considered necessary. One of the main challenges faced by current working groups is still how to provide a unified way of representing the underlying semantics and defining the vocabulary to be used by the system, thereby allowing precise knowledge transfer for problem-solving and unambiguous communications between heterogeneous, autonomous systems.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I support the development and promoting adoption of the IEEE P1872.3 standard, which is a logical extension to the IEEE 1872.2 and CORA ontology by defining additional ontologies appropriate for Autonomous Robotics (AuR).

It allows me more effective participation bringing in knowledge and perspective from the European RTD ecosystem related to robotics and automation but also with the application domain of ICT for Health and Active and Assisted Living. In particular, this fellowship addresses "ICT for Healthcare" and "eHealth, healthy living and ageing". This activity is expected to influence the preparation of a technology-oriented standard by sharing concerns and requirements that may be relevant for future adoption of the standard in concrete solutions targeting these sectors.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

SMEs related to robotics and/or developing artificial agents with a certain degree of autonomy can be impacted by this contribution, as the standard being developed aims to bring added value for integration and interoperability in solutions based on robotic and autonomous systems.

Impact on Society

The activity aims to significantly contribute to the development and revision of standards, specifically the newly accepted IEEE P1955, which addresses 6G Empowering Robotics, and IEEE P1872.3, which extends IEEE 1872.2-2021 with specific domain ontologies and new concepts related to artificial intelligence, machine learning, and human-machine interaction. Additionally, it will promote the adoption of existing standards like IEEE 1872.2-2021. This activity will actively engage in the creation and revision of new standards, including developing resources, use cases, and technical documentation that facilitate the adoption and implementation of these standards across various healthcare and technology sectors.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to two new standards: P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots and IEEE 1872.2-2021 - Standard for Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The contribution is in progress with the participation of several official and working meetings, as well as contributing to the collaboration in publications of working groups.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037/>

 <https://sagroups.ieee.org/1872-2/>

5. Societal challenges

Towards standardization of air quality sensor systems

Sergi Udina

*Senior Researcher and sensors expert, Bettair Cities
Spain*

Sector

Digital health, healthy living and ageing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN TC/264 Air quality WG41 Emissions and ambient air -
Instrumental odour monitoring
CEN TC/264 WG42 Ambient air - Air quality sensors

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship targets the implementation of the European air quality directive requires development of related technical guidelines and harmonisation, CEN/TC264/WG42 addresses that, so far with the issue of TS17660-1 and TS17660-2, which are available since December 2024.

In particular, after issuing a technical specification for the measurement of toxic gases and particulate matter, WG42 is looking into Quality Assurance and Quality Control (QA/QC) practices (a main market concern) and mobile air quality sensors (in increasing demand).

Moreover, citizens may see their right to breathe clean air and to be free from unpleasant odors are compromised by a lack of regulation and technical resources to determine liability and to faithfully establish a situation of violation. CEN/TC264/WG41 addresses that situation to help industries determine their olfactory impacts using sound and reliable technical methods, and thus allow a clear regulatory framework to be established.

In general, the topic of air quality measurements using sensors lacks mechanisms to offer trust to users, industries, and institutions. Both CEN/TC264/WG41 and WG42 address that for two slightly different problems: air pollution and odorous nuisances.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In the framework of this fellowship, I contribute the the ongoing work of two working groups. Firstly, to CEN/TC264/WG42 has issued the technical specifications TS17660-1 and TS17660-2, the latter published this last December 2024, WG42 is currently working towards a Technical Report dealing with QA/QC protocols.

Secondly, to CEN/TC264/WG41, where we are making progress to a draft document by end of this year with the aim to issue a standard.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

There are many European SMEs trying to tackle the challenge of air quality in different ways

and environment. In general, SMEs have a harder time generating trust than large companies due to fewer resources in communication, the availability of reliable protocols, metrics and institutions to establish the quality of sensor systems is paramount to aid SMEs in building trust in their products. The trust wheel starts spinning with good protocols and standards, and this is what this work aims to do in both aspects for air pollutants and olfactory nuisances.

Impact on Society

This standardisation effort on air quality has several societal key impacts, including:

- ▶ Improved evidence-based policy making by ensuring sensor data reliability.
- ▶ Environmental awareness as a motor for environmental behaviour change by making air quality measurements affordable to a larger community.
- ▶ At a large scale, healthier living in cities by improving the common awareness of the air quality of cities and possible mitigation actions.
- ▶ More sustainable industrial activity by improving the knowledge about generated pollution and odour nuisances.
- ▶ Improved data availability for scientific models, early warning and forecasting by ensuring larger availability with lower cost systems, with sufficient data quality and accuracy.
- ▶ The possibility to enforce effective compliance regarding odorous emissions with improved, cost-effective methods.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, the document in preparation under CEN TC 264/ WG41 aims to be proposed as a draft standard.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Establishing optimal best practices for the field of air quality ensures that Europe can stay on track of its SDG goals and draw a clear path towards them. This is particularly relevant in a global scenario where free trade is threatened and the added value of scientifically sound, technically solid and formally traceable practices of excellence is the best argument to compete globally.

From the perspective of this fellowship, the technical specification from WG42 needs to foster adoption and WG42 will be required to assist in that, and continue work towards a much needed technical report on QA/QC

WG41 approaches a crucial moment of definition of the new draft standard, and is needing as much support as it can get since there is still a lot to do and little time to do it to get to the draft proposal by 4th quarter of this year.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6245&cs=117BA2254E50182356461DD64BD01CC05

Participation in IEC TC 62/SC 62D/JWG 35/36 and TC 62/SC 62A/JWG 9 (Medical Robots and Medical AI)

Jan Veneman

*Head of Development / Risk Manager / Coordinator Technical Research Collaborations, Hocoma Medical GmbH
Switzerland*

Sector

Digital health, healthy living and ageing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEC TC62 Standards for medical devices WG9 Medical equipment, software, and systems using degree of autonomy and IEC SC62D JWG 36 Medical robots for rehabilitation, both linked to ISO/TC 299

Role (chair, convener, member)

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Over the past decade, the IEC 60601 series introduced a dedicated technical report addressing safety of medical electrical equipment that incorporates autonomous functions, alongside two standards covering basic safety and essential performance for medical robots (surgical and rehabilitation). In the current work, these documents are being revised to new editions in order to reflect the state of the art in a rapidly evolving field. The updates directly support EU priorities for the safe uptake of robotics and AI in healthcare and help close identified gaps for medical electrical devices.

Compared with the first editions, beyond a general technical refresh, the revisions introduce, clarify, or expand on topics such as: Classification of autonomy, battery safety, and head-mounted displays in rehab; integration of HMD-related safety and performance considerations into rehabilitation use cases.

These changes improve consistency of requirements and evaluations, supporting EU regulatory objectives for robust risk management and safer deployment of AI-enabled, robotic medical electrical equipment.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship has supported my active participation in international standardization for ICT-enabled medical electrical equipment and robotics. Specifically, I contributed to (and monitored) the following IEC/ISO joint activities:

- ▶ IEC TC 62/SC 62D/JWG 36 (liaison with ISO/TC 299/JWG 5): Medical robots for rehabilitation *Maintained: IEC 80601-2-78, Medical electrical equipment — Part 2-78: Requirements for basic safety and essential performance of medical robots for rehabilitation, assessment, compensation, or alleviation.* Contribution: participation in working sessions, technical review of drafts, and input from rehabilitation practice to align safety/performance requirements with clinical use.

- ▶ IEC TC 62/SC 62A/JWG 9 (liaison with ISO/TC 299/JWG 5): Degree of autonomy in medical equipment, software, and systems *Maintained*: IEC 60601-4-1, *Medical electrical equipment and medical electrical systems employing a degree of autonomy — Guidance and interpretation*. Contribution: engagement in discussions on autonomy classification and guidance text to support consistent application across robotic/AI-enabled devices.
- ▶ IEC TC 62/SC 62D/JWG 35 (liaison with ISO/TC 299/JWG 5): Medical robots for surgery *Maintained*: IEC 80601-2-77, *Medical electrical equipment — Part 2-77: Requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of robotically assisted surgical equipment*. Contribution: passive monitoring to ensure coherence with rehabilitation robotics requirements and awareness of cross-cutting issues.

This involvement supports the coherence of ICT-related safety and performance requirements across rehabilitation and surgical robotics and devices with autonomous functions, improving interoperability of guidance between IEC/ISO committees and helping align future revisions with clinical realities and EU regulatory expectations.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Europe hosts a vibrant ecosystem of start-ups and SMEs developing rehabilitation robots - systems that support relearning functional movement after neurological injury or disease. Under the EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR), manufacturers must demonstrate compliance with the state of the art for safety and performance. For devices within scope, IEC 80601-2-78 has become the key benchmark for basic safety and essential performance of rehabilitation robots.

Following publication of the first edition (2019), the joint working group initiated a second-edition revision to incorporate early implementation feedback and advances in technology. As this revision progresses toward Committee Draft closure, small manufacturers can expect clearer, more practicable requirements, reducing ambiguity in design inputs, verification planning, and conformity assessment. In parallel, IEC 60601-4-1 (Technical Report) provides a shared framework to characterize and manage degrees of autonomy in medical electrical equipment and systems. current development practices with where general safety requirements are heading.

Overall, these initiatives close critical gaps for European SMEs by clarifying expectations around robotic and AI-enabled rehabilitation devices, helping them accelerate safe market access, contain compliance costs, and remain competitive across EU and global markets.

Impact on Society

Rehabilitation robotics are among the earliest real-world uses of medical robots and have paved the way for broader adoption of robotics and AI in healthcare and daily living environments with vulnerable users. Clear, harmonised safety requirements and reproducible test methods are essential - not only to protect patients and clinicians, but also to give manufacturers and providers the confidence to deploy these technologies responsibly. By codifying “state-of-the-art” expectations, the standards framework enables innovation while safeguarding users.

Societal benefits enabled by robust standards include:

- ▶ Patient safety and dignity: Defined limits, fail-safe behaviours, and human-robot interaction requirements reduce the risk of harm and ensure predictable performance in rehabilitation settings.
- ▶ Healthcare access: Standardised safety/performance criteria help scale high-quality therapy beyond specialised centres, supporting adoption in regional hospitals and community care.
- ▶ Clinician support and quality of care: Reliable, well-tested systems can deliver high-dose, repeatable training while reducing therapist physical strain, freeing time for complex clinical tasks.
- ▶ Public trust and uptake: Transparent, consensus-based requirements underpin procurement, reimbursement, and clinical guidelines—building societal confidence in robotic care.

- ▷ Innovation with accountability: Clear targets shorten development cycles, lower compliance ambiguity for SMEs, and focus competition on outcomes and usability rather than ad-hoc safety interpretations.

The degree-of-autonomy guidance further generalises these protections to *any* medical product using robotic or AI technologies. By providing a common language for autonomy levels and the associated safety controls and human oversight, it supports ethically aligned, trustworthy deployment of AI-enabled medical devices across care pathways, from clinics to homes.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. In my role representing Hocoma and Motek (Swiss/European rehabilitation-technology manufacturers) and IISART (industry association for advanced rehabilitation technology), and drawing on my experience as former coordinator of a COST Action on Wearable Robots, I have tabled concrete, manufacturer-oriented proposals within the relevant IEC/ISO joint working groups. My contributions focus on making requirements clear, implementable, and testable so SMEs and larger manufacturers can apply them unambiguously.

These inputs are intended to inform the ongoing revisions (e.g., IEC 80601-2-78 and autonomy guidance under IEC 60601-4-1) and to improve consistency, testability, and regulatory defensibility across the standards landscape.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The standards work is mid-stream and will require sustained, coordinated effort to reach impact in clinics and industry:

- ▷ Complete the revisions pipeline: Advance IEC 80601-2-78 towards publication, with systematic resolution of comments and alignment with ISO/TC 299. In parallel, progress IEC 60601-4-1 to support and feed into IEC 60601-1 (4th ed.) over the coming years.
- ▷ Ensure EU harmonization and coherence: Early liaison with CEN/CENELEC for EN adoption and MDR Annex Z mapping; maintain consistency across related standards (e.g., -2-77 surgical robots, ISO 14971, IEC 62366-1, IEC 62304, IEC 60601-1-2).
- ▷ Operationalize autonomy guidance: Pilot the level-of-autonomy scale on representative devices, define evidence expectations per level (risk controls, human oversight, verification/validation), and align with evolving EU AI Act requirements.
- ▷ Address cross-cutting technologies: Mature guidance for battery systems (exoskeletons), HMD integration, connectivity/cybersecurity (e.g., IEC 81001-5-1/80001-1), and safe human-robot interaction in rehab settings.

Together, these activities will deliver a robust, harmonized standards base that protects patients and clinicians while accelerating safe innovation in rehabilitation robotics and AI-enabled medical electrical devices.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:14:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:12533,25#

 https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:14:416679820428529:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:7896,25

Simulation in Additive Manufacturing- Guidance on computational methods for manufacturing industry

Noel Harrison

*Associate Professor in Mechanical Engineering, University of Galway
Ireland*

Sector

Digitisation of European Industry

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO TC 261 Additive manufacturing WG4 Data and Design, and JG73
Digital product definition and data management

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship is focused on the development of a new standard within the combined ISO /TC 261 and ASTM F42 Additive Manufacturing (AM) committee structures. There is a clear need for standardisation in the emerging technology of AM. Since it was established in 2011, ISO/TC 261 Additive Manufacturing has published 46 standards for industry in areas such as health and safety, feedstocks and qualification. Such work has enabled European industry to adopt, for example, metal AM (metal 3D printing) into some of the most highly regulated sectors such as medical devices and aerospace.

Much of the AM research community across Europe (for example I-Form, the Research Ireland Centre for Advanced Manufacturing) utilises advanced digital simulation and computational modelling techniques as a tool to understand, troubleshoot, optimise and further advance our AM capabilities (e.g. Finite Element Analysis, Computational Fluid Dynamics, Molecular Dynamics). There is however a disconnect between the activities, methods expertise and outputs of the research community, and current industry practices. Put simply, industry has not been empowered to deploy digital methods, such as computational simulations of AM materials within their internal manufacturing processes. To date, the consensus and guidance provided by ISO and ASTM activities in AM are largely limited to qualification based on experimental testing methods. There is a significant dearth of guidance when it comes to computational simulation methods as a testing and process improvement tool. Filling this gap would constitute a significant effort in digitisation of Europe's AM industry.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The key result of my fellowship is the establishment of a new series of standards on simulation (computational modelling) of AM process and products that have undergone AM fabrication. This will be a new line of standards that will complement the current Terminology (WG1), Processes, systems and materials (WG2), Test methods and quality specifications (WG3) Data and Design (WG4), Environment, health and safety (WG6) working groups (WG) within ISO TC 261. The current WGs were established in the last 12 years to meet the immediate needs of industries adopting AM as a manufacturing process. Looking forward- the new

immediate need is clear- the AM industry require guidance on how to leverage the wealth of computational modelling and simulation capability that has emerged from academic and commercial software providers in recent times.

ISO standards can ensure that simulation models accurately represent real-world AM processes, enabling manufacturers to predict and mitigate potential defects before production and provide a guideline to industry as to what extent quality issues are likely to be encountered, and how best to mitigate or address such issues.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The development of ISO standards in simulation will help lower entry barriers for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which are critical to the European economy. Standardization simplifies the learning curve and reduces the cost of adopting AM technologies by providing clear guidelines and best practices for operating the machines. SMEs can leverage standardized simulation tools to optimize their designs and production processes, fostering innovation and enabling competition with larger players.

In this sense, this work provides guidance to all companies on how to utilize modelling in the AM process chain.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. The proposed title of the new draft standard is: "Additive Manufacturing – General principles - Overview of modelling and simulation".

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The first document is heading for approval as a New Work Item proposal status. A core group of experts and large working group of advisors have been established. The large working group were surveyed for their interests and needs in simulation and modelling in AM, and this data has been captured and analysed.

The priority for this project is to produce an overall guidance document for industry on simulation and modelling in AM. This document will be a general principles overview of modelling and simulation in AM. The document specifies terms and definitions for describing computational models that simulate AM processes or simulate the performance of materials with characteristics typical of AM processes. It also provides guidelines on applications of computational modelling where predictions can be used to support decisions in the AM process chain, and guidelines for sources of calibration and input data.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/629086.html

Global Health and Wellbeing Standard for Sustainable Cities: Integrating Digital Health

Diana Soeiro

*Researcher and Consultant, Instituto Português de Qualidade - IPQ
Portugal*

Sector

Digital health, healthy living and ageing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 268 Sustainable cities and communities
Management Systems.

Sustainable WG1

Role

National convener of ISO TC 268 WG1

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my role as the national , coordinator of the Portuguese delegation ISO/TC 268 WG1. This works focuses on supporting the development of ISO 37128.

Regarding this standardisation project, there is a disconnection between available experts and those formally nominated for SDO voting, resulting in underrepresentation. For instance, France (AFNOR) has been active but without a formally nominated expert, and Mauritius (MSB) withdrew its nomination due to lack of support.

Therefore, the priority is increasing expert engagement, especially from developing countries, is critical to ensure diverse and comprehensive participation in standardization processes.

With this regard, the key challenge is that the expert availability is uneven—while infrastructure and equipment topics attract more attention, management systems, which are often vital for cities and communities, receive less focus and oversight. Bridging this gap is necessary to develop standards that meet real-world urban needs.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship contributes to the ICT standards landscape by supporting the development of ISO 37128 within the newly established Joint Technical Committee JTC 4 (a merge between TC 268, EC SyC Electrotechnical Aspects of Smart Cities and ISO/ IEC JTC 1 Information Technology /WG11 Smart Cities), effective January 2026. This new committee focuses on sustainable and smart cities and communities, ensuring the standard integrates digital technologies, including digital health solutions and urban well-being indicators. The work aligns with key standards such as ISO/IEEE 11073 (Digital Health Device Communication) and ISO 37120 (Sustainable Development Indicators for Cities).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The contribution directly impacts European societies and SMEs by helping develop standards that promote healthier, more sustainable, and inclusive urban environments. These standards support cities in improving well-being, resilience, and equitable access

to services—key factors for vibrant communities and local economies. For SMEs, clearer guidelines on sustainability and smart urban solutions create opportunities for innovation, market access, and competitiveness within Europe. By fostering alignment between global best practices and local needs, the work helps European stakeholders adapt to evolving challenges in urban development and public health.

Impact on Society

By promoting interoperability and scalable health and well-being indicators, this initiative advances inclusive, data-driven solutions for sustainable urban development. I contribute extensively by providing guidance on integrating existing management system elements and concerns with technology—particularly emphasizing digital health and IoT integration—to promote health and well-being effectively within urban management systems.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, leading the development of ISO 37128 for sustainable, smart cities integrating digital health.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Between April 7th, 2025 and June 30th, 2025 a ballot was formally open at ISO TC 268 level, featuring purpose, justification and outline of the standard being given the reference number ISO NP 37128. The standard was formally partially approved as a work item by a 2/3 majority of the P-members of the committees voting. However, full approval requires a minimum number of experts who are available and willing to actively engage in the process. Current status: Therefore, on July 19th, 2025 an additional 4-week ballot for additional participation was opened. Formal results of the ballot will be out in mid-August. Because at least France will formally nominate experts, the standard's approval is highly likely.

When approved, a first meeting will be scheduled for mid-September, during which a more detailed version of the proposed outline will be presented and discussed. The draft is currently under development and will continue to be refined in the lead-up to that meeting.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/656906.html>

StandICT.eu 2026 has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe (HE) research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101091933.